

- **YOUTH**
How to Engage for a Brighter Future
- **ENTREPRENEURSHIP**
Great Ideas for Pro-poor Businesses
- **KEY DATA**
Facts and Figures
- **STATE OF PLAY**
Best Policies and the “Demographic Dividend”

Empowered lives.
Resilient nations.

SouthernInnovator

A magazine celebrating South-South innovation

ISSUE 02

SPRING 2012

www.southerninnovator.org

Youth & Entrepreneurship Issue

How youth and entrepreneurship can help in the push to meet the MDGs

Check out
the Southern Innovator website
for more content and updates:
www.southerninnovator.org

Empowered lives.
Resilient nations.

About UNDP

The United Nations Development Programme (UNDP) is the UN's global development network, an organization advocating for change and connecting countries to knowledge, experience and resources to help people build a better life.

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Southern Innovator

Welcome to the second issue of **Southern Innovator**. Our first issue, in May 2011, covered the dynamic and fast-changing world of mobile phones and information technology for development. This issue features entrepreneurs who are tackling the challenge of youth unemployment by cleverly applying business models to boost incomes, increase prosperity and reduce poverty.

The world today faces a paradox. The world now has the largest number of young people that it has ever known, representing an enormous potential for growth. Yet these youth live mostly in the global South, where unemployment levels for young people have been rising during the global economic crisis. And for those youth who are working, many earn a meagre living in poor conditions. In short, they are not fulfilling their potential and this is one of the greatest challenges of our time.

The stories in this issue were chosen for the inspired thinking and business solutions that they bring to a common concern: poverty and unemployment. Not all these businesses will survive. They operate in difficult social and economic conditions and therefore readers should recall the Latin warning “caveat emptor” – buyer beware – which still applies everywhere in the world.

This issue of **Southern Innovator** shows how unleashing the potential and actual ingenuity of youth can give a much-needed jolt to efforts to achieve development goals. And this includes the Millennium Development Goals.

There are also a number of new features in this second issue. We have included more visual resources to make it easier to digest lessons learned captured in the magazine and to grasp what other resources can be tapped into in order to get your enterprise off the ground.

In each issue of **Southern Innovator** you will find contact information for further follow-up. We have attempted to provide the most current information, but given the quick pace of change in the global South, this is not always possible. We apologize in advance for any out-of-date information, including Internet links. We hope that this magazine makes a useful contribution to your work and helps to inspire all concerned to act!

Cosmas Gitta
Editor-in-Chief
Southern Innovator
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Youth & Entrepreneurship

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A Young World

Seeking a Brighter Future

GLOBAL UNEMPLOYMENT

200 million (2011)

GLOBAL YOUTH UNEMPLOYMENT

75.1 million (2010)

70.5 million (2007)

349 million

Africans between 15 and 24 years of age by 2050

29%

of world total

90%

in developing world

1.8 billion

youth between

10 and 24

GETTING BETTER CONNECTED IN THE SOUTH

1.8 billion youth in the world with a mobile phone

6 billion mobile phone subscriptions in the world

1/3 of world's population is online

45% of Internet users are below 25

82% of world population not using Internet (2006)

65% of world population not using Internet (2011)

37% of population in China using Internet (2011)

62% of world's Internet users in developing countries (2011), up from 44% in 2006

70% of youth or 1.9 billion people under 25 in developing countries are not online

Source: ITU

SNAPSHOT OF GLOBAL FLIGHT PATTERNS AS OF OCTOBER 2008

- Number of global take-offs May 2007: 2.5 million (Quarterly Airline Traffic Statistics).
- The largest year-on-year rise in take-offs was recorded in China in 2007.
- Flights between Western Europe and Africa were up 13% in 2007.
- In 2010, global passenger traffic rose 6.6%, reaching the 5 billion passenger mark for the first time (Airports Council International).

7
billion
(2011): World population

(2011): World population

40%: World's population below age of 20
– biggest cohort of youth in human history.

WORLD TRADE

More than doubled:
share of world goods trade among
developing countries

7% (1990)

17% (2009)

40% of all South-South
commerce is carried out by China

Source: ADB

SOUTH-SOUTH TRADE

China-Africa trade

US \$10 billion (2000)

US \$108.84 billion (2008)

Source: WTO

Africa's consumer class:
300 million people

152 million

young people – a quarter
of the world's young
workers – are employed
but are in extreme
poverty in households
living on US \$1.25 a
person per day in 2008
(ILO)

Majority

of young people in South
Asia and sub-Saharan
Africa are working at any job
they can, many working long
hours under poor
conditions in the informal
economy.
(ILO)

Youth

Introduction

A crisis is facing youth around the globe in both developed and developing countries. In developed countries, youth unemployment rates have been growing despite low or declining birth rates and youth's falling share of the ageing population. In the developing countries, the biggest youth population in the world's history represents a great opportunity; one that, if seized, can give a powerful boost to achieving the Millennium Development Goals as they approach their deadline in 2015.

This issue of **Southern Innovator** contains a snapshot of some of the stories published in the monthly e-newsletter **Development Challenges, South-South Solutions**. Researching the e-newsletter since 2007 has unearthed a wealth of resources, shedding light on many opportunities for engaging youth to meet development goals.

One fact comes across time and time again: youth want to work and contribute to their societies, but often they are working in a way that is not bringing high economic benefits to them and their families. Many work in the informal sector, undertaking hard work requiring few sophisticated skills and doing entrepreneurial activities driven more by enthusiasm and need than by clever business plans and models. The stories gathered here show that things do not have to be this way.

There are now 1.8 billion youth between the ages of 10 and 24 in the world, and 90 per cent of them are in the developing world. As the stories in this section show, finding the right way to engage them can pay big dividends for these countries.

The boundaries and names shown, and the designations used on this map do not imply official endorsement or acceptance by the United Nations.

*Dotted line represents approximately the Line of Control in Jammu and Kashmir agreed upon by India and Pakistan. The final status of Jammu and Kashmir has not yet been agreed upon by the parties.

**Appears without prejudice to the question of sovereignty.

***A dispute exists between the Governments of Argentina and the United Kingdom of Great Britain and Northern Ireland concerning sovereignty over the Falkland Islands (Malvinas).

The initials in parentheses refer to the administering Power or the Power involved in a special treaty relationship

Next Generation of Innovation for the Grass Roots

Taking inspiration from science fiction sagas, the next generation of innovation is already taking shape in the South. A group of innovative facilities called **Fab Labs** (short for Fabrication Laboratories) in Ghana, India, Kenya, South Africa and Costa Rica is applying cutting-edge technology to address people's everyday needs.

Like the futuristic "replicator" in American television and film science-fiction series Star Trek, Fab Labs enable people to design and produce what they need there and then. The labs are mushrooming throughout the South as people get the innovation bug.

Originally an idea from the **Massachusetts Institute of Technology's Center for Bits and Atoms**, which sponsors nine of the labs, Fab Labs let people use digital technology to build physical objects, from eyeglass frames to toys and computer parts. Fab Labs empower local invention by turning education, problem-solving and job creation into a creative process.

With minimal training, children and adults are designing and making their own toys, jewellery and even computer circuit boards with the machines. It is turning people from consumers into inventors. – (October 2007)

fab.cba.mit.edu

Quick Facts

- 100 million jobs need to be created in the Middle East and North Africa by 2020 to meet the demand for work.
- 130 million people between 15 and 24 cannot read or write.
- A poll found that 1 in 5 African youth (15 to 24) without a business wanted to start one.
- Indian animation sector overall turnover in 2009: US \$950 million.
- Indian computer gaming industry overall turnover in 2009: US \$300 million (from US \$30 million in 2005).
- Average fee earned by a musician at a Brazilian "tecnobrega" party: US \$919.

Q & A

SI There are many initiatives to breach the digital divide: What is different about your approach and what can you do that is currently being missed by other NGOs/initiatives/global agencies?

Our NGO is completely grass roots. We train the people who train the people. It is an each-one-teach-one philosophy and is highly effective. We also design our projects to be self-sustainable after one year of successful implementation.

SI Why focus on content for the Internet? Why not just stick with traditional publishing for underserved areas?

The Internet puts the choice of content at the fingertips of the user. Traditional media are one-way communications. Internet is bidirectional.

Crystal "Naliaka" Watley Kigoni
Executive Director
Voices of Africa for Sustainable Development

voicesofafrica.org

Arab World Domain Name Opportunity

It is easy to miss a new economic opportunity. The introduction of an Arabic domain name system for the Internet is just such an opportunity.

Since the dawn of the Internet, Latin script has been used exclusively for top-level web domain names, the addresses that end .com, .org and so on. That has been a big obstacle for users of non-Latin script languages such as Arabic.

The explosion in mobile phones in the Arab world has dramatically increased the number of people who can access the Internet.

However, it is estimated just 10 per cent of people in the Arab world speak English, leaving them unable to access the many resources on the Internet. But by turning to using Arabic domain names, there will be consistency and no more guesswork for Arabic-speaking web users. – (July 2011)

African Internet Opportunity

Africa's Internet opportunities are only just starting. **Wired** – the technology magazine – is calling this "a once-in-a-lifetime opportunity to build the next Zyngas, eBays and Groupons for a huge untapped local market". As new broadband fibre optic undersea cables are laid along the continent's coasts, it's "like being back in 1995", **Wired** claims.

The 10,000 kilometre East African Submarine Cable System (EASSy), connecting sub-Saharan Africa with Europe and Asia, has joined other cables from the continent. Gradually, the infrastructure is falling into place to connect Africa properly to the rest of the world.

CROSS-SECTION OF A CABLE

Indian Mobile Phone App Innovators

With mobile phones becoming ubiquitous across the global South, the opportunity to make money – and possible fortunes – by providing "apps" for these devices is now a reality.

Apps, or applications, enable users to do everything from running a business to banking to navigating chaotic cities.

The recent **TechSparks 2011 App4India** (facebook.com/techspark) contest showcased the creative thinking about apps now happening in India.

The **India TV Guide**, based in Bangalore, India's software hub, is a mobile phone application developed by **Jini Labs** (jini.com) offering programme listings for 150 television channels broadcast in India and allowing viewers to save reminders for favourite shows and build favourites lists.

Youth Surge in the South: A Great Business Opportunity

The world has record numbers of youth but a crisis of imagination exists, where many countries have not found a way to apply this energy and talent to achieve development goals.

The world's youth population (those between the ages of 12 and 24) has now reached a historical high of 1.5 billion – 1.3 billion of whom are in developing countries (**World Development Report 2007**). Nearly half of the world's unemployed are youth, and the Middle East and North Africa alone must create 100 million jobs by 2020 to meet demand for work.

Some 130 million people between the ages of 15 and 24 cannot read or write. This enormous cohort of talent and energy in many countries of the South goes untapped. Many youth lack access to quality employment and educational opportunities. Yet knowledge of business could make the difference between success and failure for these young people, especially when they come from poor families with few choices. Business is also a great way to help harder-to-reach young people such as child soldiers, young girls, youth affected by HIV/AIDS, gang members and orphans.

“The youth bulge is happening and it is an enormous opportunity or an enormous challenge: how are all these young people going to have productive and valuable livelihoods and contribute to their communities?”, said **Fiona Macauley**, founder and president of a US-based consulting firm, **Making Cents International**, working with entrepreneurs. “Policy makers are only just realizing they need a change of perspective on health issues, issues of poverty, the education system – all of it needs to respond.”

Micro-entrepreneurship, where risk is low and the amount invested small, offers the most realistic route into business

for youth in countries where more formal opportunities are absent. While concepts like micro-credit and social lending have taken off, youth have not received the attention they deserve, according to Macauley. She has also found that financial services need to change to encourage youth to save, while also opening up to give them access to credit for micro-entrepreneurship.

To address this problem, Making Cents organized a landmark **Youth Microenterprise Conference** from September 1 to 12, 2007 in Washington, D.C., in order to start building the links and networks between groups working with youth businesses and to build a global movement for economic development of youth. It tackled three themes: the role of youth, sector strategies, and building partnerships. It kicked off a new approach to youth and

The problem of child soldiers is most critical in Africa, where children as young as nine have been involved in armed conflicts.

Source: child-soldiers.org

In many countries, child labour is mainly an agricultural issue. Worldwide 60 per cent of all child labourers in the age group 5 to 17 years work in agriculture.

Source: ILO

Youth unemployment is a problem across the world. Every year the world needs to find work for an additional 40 million youth.

Source: WEF

Growing enrolment in primary education over the past decade has led to increased demand for secondary education.

Source: UNESCO

entrepreneurship that has gone from strength to strength in the years since. Making Cents has built a vast treasure trove of resources for youth, entrepreneurs, educators, policymakers and NGOs.

"It is important that entrepreneurship is mainstreamed into the school system", continues Macauley. "That youth are getting good skills the private sector is looking for: how to budget, costing and pricing, developing entrepreneurial mind sets, problem-solving, leading groups, researching, how to be problem solvers. If we can get this into the high school and the elementary school level, imagine how different the workforce would be?"

Other initiatives are focusing on youth entrepreneurship: **South African Breweries Limited** has been providing seed capital to youth businesses run by 18 to 35 year olds through its **KickStart** programme. Successful youth enterprises to come out of the programme have included Golden Sunset Fresh Produce, started by 27-year-old **Alwyn Jepha** to help pay for his law school studies. Starting on a small scale producing vegetables and fruit, the business has grown substantially, making in a month what it once made in a year. The KickStart grant enabled Jepha to buy irrigation equipment and to scale up his operations. At Zanopt, **Khetla Leqola** has been producing Afro-centric optical frame styles, meeting a market need not being met by the global brands. KickStart enabled Leqola to buy the equipment required to produce the frames and run his office.

“ The youth bulge is happening and it is an enormous opportunity or an enormous challenge ”

The **Barbados Youth Business Trust** has an excellent web portal for youth, with practical tips on starting a youth business and good examples of young people actually doing it. At 29, youth entrepreneur **Ailene Harrison-Malcolm** found herself unemployed. She had long noticed the lack of clothing for full-bodied women in Barbados and decided to open her own store, Full Elegance Boutique, in 2002. She was able to tap into a mentoring scheme run by the Government's Youth Entrepreneurship Scheme to get a loan. It is this kind of joint support that youth need. – (May 2007)

•**World Development Report 2007: Development and the Next Generation:**

Website: tinyurl.com/bs8zI

•**World Bank's Youthink! Website for youth:** Full of research, knowledge and experience gathered by World Bank experts on international development.

Website: youthink.worldbank.org

•**The Entrepreneurial League System:** Professor Thomas S. Lyons and Gregg A. Lichtenstein have established an entrepreneurial mentor scheme based on the baseball farm team concept targeting poor communities.

Website: entreleaguesystem.com

•**Students in Free Enterprise (SIFE):** A non-profit organization in 40 countries, it organizes students on university campuses to develop community outreach projects that achieve their five goals: market economics, success skills, entrepreneurship, financial literacy and business ethics. **Website:** sife.org

African Youth Want to Do Business in Fast-growing Economy

Africa's growing economy is gaining momentum from an optimistic young population keen to start businesses. At least that is what a 2011 poll of African youth says, finding that one in five Africans between the ages of 15 and 24 without a current business wants to start one in the next 12 months.

The Gallup-survey of 27 African countries and areas also found that young women were just as keen as young men to start a business.

Over the past decade, Africa experienced an average economic growth rate of 5.4 per cent (World Bank) - a big gain from the poor growth rates of the 1980s and early 1990s.

The turnaround in Africa's economic prospects is the product of a number of trends and factors. One has been better policies and easier trade. Other contributors include rising tourism, a growing service sector, rising commodity prices, greater demand for African exports in emerging economies and rapidly improving communications: the surge in mobile phone usage during the last five years has surprised many. Africans are also avid spenders on goods and services, spending US \$860 billion on them in 2008, more than India's US \$635 billion or the Russian Federation's US \$821 billion (**Economic Report on Africa 2011**).

The African Development Bank predicts Africa's growth rate for 2011 will decline to 3.7 per cent from 2010's 4.9 per cent, largely as a result of turmoil in North Africa. East Africa is projected to grow the fastest in 2011 at 6.7 per cent, with West Africa close behind at 5.9 per cent.

Africa as a continent collectively had a gross domestic product in 2009 of US \$1.6 trillion: equal to Brazil's or the Russian Federation's. The continent is considered among the fastest-expanding economic regions in the world (McKinsey & Company).

In fact, while economic prospects are grim in many developed countries, Africa and Asia are the only continents to grow during this recession. But major problems still confront the continent, among them youth unemployment. Those between 15 and 24 make up more than 60 per cent of the continent's population and are 45 per cent of the total labour force (**African Economic Outlook**). Sub-Saharan Africa is experiencing a youth explosion, with the proportion of youth there to rise to 75 per cent of the population by 2015. Demographers forecast that this rising youth trend will not stop for the next 20 years.

Getting these youth actively engaged in the economy and society is a major challenge for the continent. At present 133 million African youth are illiterate. They have few skills and are marginalized from more productive sectors of the economy.

Even those with an education often find that their skills do not match the needs of the labour market. In sub-Saharan Africa, youth unemployment is believed to be 20 per cent.

So even with better economic prospects and growing economies and incomes, youth unemployment looms large.

The **Economic Report on Africa 2011** finds that the →

Micro-entrepreneurialism and Youth

Understanding what works best for youth and entrepreneurship has become the subject of intense study in the past few years. The complexity of divining what works best across a multiplicity of cultures, regions and contexts is a difficult task. One organization that has been making good progress with this task is Making Cents International. The Washington-based social enterprise is dedicated to finding the best ways for entrepreneurs and enterprises to participate in profitable markets. Some of their resources are described below.

The concept of micro-entrepreneurialism is particularly relevant for youth. Youth in general will have few resources and little experience but lots of ideas and enthusiasm. Micro everything - from micro-loans for the poor and micro-work for the poor - is about making small investments with low risk to get big results. Micro-entrepreneurs proliferate across the global South but many of their activities come from the raw need to do something to survive rather than to thrive. Enthusiasm and hard work are dented by unsophisticated business models, inability to store wealth, inability to scale up a business, poor understanding of trade opportunities, and poor understanding of finance.

However, a plethora of new resources is becoming available to support and aid micro-entrepreneurs. From Internet and mobile phone applications or "apps" to global trading platforms such as Alibaba (alibaba.com) and new services such as e-commerce service Payment (payvment.com) and community marketplace for urban dwellers Kicktable (kicktable.com), micro-entrepreneurs can tap into a wider community and better target customers, organize their businesses, and develop more sophisticated offerings and scaleup.

Educational Curriculum in 25 Plus Languages (makingcents.com/products_services/curriculum.php)

Market Opportunities™ Market Opportunities™ brings the world of value chain study into perspective for young entrepreneurs, helping them to discover market opportunities and business relationships that are critical to sustainable business growth. This curriculum provides students with the knowledge and experience that they need to take their learning beyond the classroom and into the real world.

Money Minds!™ Financial management is a fundamental life skill. Money Minds!™ is a unique curriculum designed to provide youth and adults alike with a forum to understand how their beliefs about money shape their actions *with* money as well as the opportunity to redefine their personal and financial goals and priorities.

Source: Making Cents International

→ “persistent high youth unemployment rate is a cause of concern and a potential source of political instability”. Job creation is still not adequate: “The growth rates are still below the levels needed to make a significant impact on unemployment and poverty reduction.”

While Africa will experience growth in 2011, for youth it is looking like a “jobless recovery”, according to the report. Overseas investors are mostly throwing their money at the resource sector, which does not create many jobs in the economy.

For young Africans looking to start a business, however, opportunities exist in sectors such as retailing, telecommunications, banking, infrastructure-related industries, resource-related businesses, and all along the agricultural value chain.

The booming communications industry has added 316 million new subscribers since 2000, for example. All those newly connected people need new services.

And once a business is up and running, it

is possible to make higher profits in Africa than on other continents, according to the United Nations. Africa leads the emerging market economies for returns for businesses. This is because competition is not as intense and there is still plenty of built-up consumer demand that needs to be met.

All of this means that young people willing to start a business and put in the hard work will have a better chance of reaping the rewards.
– (July 2011)

- **iHub Nairobi:** iHub Nairobi’s Innovation Hub for the technology community is an open space for the technologists, investors, tech companies and hackers in the area. This space is a tech community facility with a focus on young entrepreneurs, web and mobile phone programmers, designers and researchers. It is part open community workspace (co-working), part vector for investors and VCs and part incubator. **Website:** ihub.co.ke/pages/home.php
- **The Other Side of Innovation: Solving the Execution Challenge** by Vijay Govindarajan, Chris Trimble: On how businesses need to follow through with execution if they really want to innovate. **Website:** hbr.org/product/baynote/an/13219-HBK-ENG?referral=00505&cm_sp=baynote--featured_products--13219-HBK-ENG
- **“The Globe: Cracking the Next Growth Market: Africa”** by Mutsa Chironga et al., **Harvard Business Review.** **Website:** hbr.org/2011/05/the-globe-cracking-the-next-growth-market-africa/ar/1
- **Global Youth Economic Opportunities Conference:** **Website:** youtheconomicopportunities.org

Nairobi’s iHub celebrated its one-year anniversary in March 2011

Meet Southern Innovator

The first issue

Southern Innovator comes packed with stories, images and contact details about a new generation of pioneering innovators across the global South.

Global reach

SI is distributed around the world, from the buzzing new urban megacities of the South to the poorest places on earth.

Stories to learn from

There isn’t a better way to learn than from others in the same situation. SI’s stories share details on success and innovation and have links to resources - so readers can get down to work.

Rich infographics

Complex data and trends are transformed into clear graphics for ease of understanding.

Eye-catching illustrations and graphics

Concepts are reinforced through visual images to aid understanding.

Getting connected

Southern Innovator is packed with resources and is backed up with a website and monthly e-newsletter. Each issue is intended to provide inspiration and practical information to get started on the journey to being a Southern Innovator!

Getting teched up:
Mobile phones and
the Internet make
innovators efficient

Berber Hip Hop Helps to Re-ignite Culture and Economy

Turning to the creative economy to open up new markets and opportunities offers great potential for further increasing incomes in the global South.

Music is being used to revive the ancient language of the original North African desert dwellers, the Berbers. Along the way, the process is generating income and spawning a whole new generation of entrepreneurs.

The Berbers are North Africa's indigenous people, living primarily in Algeria, Libya, Morocco and Tunisia, but their language and culture – called Amazigh – were replaced as the lingua franca of the region after the Arab conquest in the 7th century. Centuries later, the language is enjoying resurgence under Morocco's king, **Mohammed VI**, who is helping to promote it through television programming and a new law making teaching of the language compulsory in schools by 2010.

Amazigh people – the name means “free humans” or “free people” – total more than 50 million. Their group of languages, called Tamazight, are spoken by several million people across North Africa, with the largest number in Morocco.

For young Moroccans, promoting the language is more interesting when hip hop is thrown into the mix.

Artists such as rock metal band **Hinder Minds** from Casablanca, Morocco, symbolize the vibrant music scene in the country.

- **International Young Music Entrepreneur of the Year Award:** an award from the British Council. **Website:** creativeeconomy.org.uk/UKYCE/index.asp?ID=35
The British Council also sponsors numerous awards for international creatives. **Website:** creativeeconomy.org.uk
- **The United Nations of Hip Hop:** A web portal for African hip hop news, music and resources. **Website:** unitednationsofhiphop.com
- **Festival Timitar:** The Timitar music festival happens every year in July in Agadir, Morocco. It brings together Amazigh musicians with other African and world musicians. **Website:** festival-timitar.com/timitar.html
- **Amazigh Film Festival:** The annual Amazigh Film Festival happens every year in January in Los Angeles, California, USA. **Website:** tukshop.biz

Where Berber culture was once shunned in Morocco and the language banned in schools, the revival of the Tamazight language has led to a flourishing of summer arts festivals, thriving Tamazight newspapers and Tamazight hip hop.

One hip-hop outfit, **Rap2Bled** from the Moroccan city of Agadir, sings about unemployment, drug addiction, the emancipation of women and other pressing social issues.

“My mother and grandfather don't know any Arabic...Before they couldn't watch television, read a newspaper. They hadn't got a clue what was going on in the world. They didn't know anything,” Rap2Bled singer **Aziz**, who goes by the street name Fatman, told Radio Netherlands Worldwide.

“But now there is a TV channel in our local dialect and a newspaper. But our aim is to put the language on the map by fusing it with hip hop. More than 60 per cent of young Moroccans listen only to rap and Western music. So we thought why not fuse Berber with that and make it really accessible?”

Just 10 years ago, rap and hip hop were virtually unknown in Morocco, with only a small group of hip-hop aficionados listening to big American stars such as Dr Dre, Tupac Shakur and Notorious B.I.G.

But today the hip-hop culture and way of life (of which rap and hip-hop music are a part) have become a powerful force in Moroccan culture. Moroccan rap focuses on local issues such as unemployment and injustice and is ubiquitous on radio and TV.

The **Casa Crew**, from Casablanca, has become so successful since their beginnings in 2003 that their fan base stretches to Spain and Algeria.

“Rap is a lifestyle, and mainly a culture of convictions. The fact that rap is spreading in countries like Morocco is an excellent sign”, **Caprice** from Casa Crew told the Arab Media News Menassat. – (March 2009)

Taxis Promote African Music Beats

South Africa's township music is pounding its way onto the global music charts. How has music made in the impoverished townships that are a hangover from decades of apartheid – the country's former racial separation laws, which trapped millions of black South Africans in disenfranchisement and poverty – travelled around the world? By hitching a ride with the country's ubiquitous taxi drivers.

Many South Africans are big fans of European House, a type of dance music. An enterprising group of producers living in the townships of Pretoria started to experiment, taking the House that they loved and turning it into something more reflective of where they lived. The result, dubbed Township House, blends the school-of-hard-knocks beats of South African hip-hop, or Kwaito, with House music's tempos and electronic sounds.

Coming from the townships meant that musicians behind Township House were frozen out of the mainstream music industry. And as every artist knows, if you can't get heard, then your music will go nowhere. Rejected by radio stations and big record labels, they turned to an unlikely outlet: taxis, the small minibuses that are the only alternative form of transportation for people who do not have a car.

They are heavily used: the University of Pretoria estimates that between 5 and 10 million people use minibus taxis every day to get to work or get around.

"In South Africa, the easiest way to the people is through the taxis", musician DJ Qness told CNN.

The vast network of taxis serving the country represents a captive audience of listeners. Many are simply bored as they endure lengthy commutes. The Township House producers handed out compact discs (CDs) of their tracks to taxi drivers to play. They soon had a hit on their hands but without any presence in record stores people couldn't buy the CDs that they wanted. So a new source of income was born for taxi drivers: selling CDs from their taxi stands or roadside stalls.

With appetites whetted for Township House, it started to outsell imported dance music.

The biggest hit maker of this pioneering group was DJ Mujava, whose track 'Township Funk' was a global dance club hit in 2008.

Africa's taxi minibuses are used by millions every day to get to and from work. Often packed with people, they jostle for customers in a chaotic scene played out across the continent. In South Africa, entrepreneurs are using this captive audience to give local musicians an edge and reach new listeners.

"These people created a demand. The Mujava's 'Township Funk' blew up on the streets and everything went crazy", said Qness, who works for record label Sheer Music. – (June 2009)

- **DJ Mujava:** Listen to all of DJ Mujava's tracks at his website. **Website:** myspace.com/mujava
- **DigiArts Africa:** The DigiArts Africa network is a tool to find people working in Digital Arts in Africa and to provide a collaborative working space to promote digital arts in Africa. **Website:** portal.unesco.org/culture/en/ev.php-URL_ID=5346&URL_DO=DO_TOPIC&URL_SECTION=201.html
- **African Musicians Profiles:** A lively website featuring profiles of African musicians by alphabetical listing and also reviews of African films. **Website:** africanmusiciansprofiles.com
- **Recording Industry of South Africa (RiSA):** RiSA is the main body representing the South African recording industry. **Website:** risa.org.za

Mobile Phone Downloads Help Musicians

African musicians hoping to support themselves through their recordings have always had to contend with the added burden of poor copyright control over their work. Global audiences know of the success of artists like **Fela Kuti, Youssou N'Dour, Manu Dibango** and **Miriam Makeba**, but most African musicians can look forward to scant earnings from recording their music.

Anyone who has walked through the markets of Africa will know that there are plenty of pirated CDs for sale, yet it is of no use to a musician who never sees the money. While music is a global business worth US \$40 billion according to the Recording Industry Association of America, pirated music in Africa is rampant: some estimates by the Recording Industry of South Africa put it at over 80 per cent of available music. The estimated daily income of a pirate music vendor in Africa ranges between Euros 762 (US \$965) and Euros 2,744 (US \$3,476).

But a solution to this problem is being pioneered in Botswana in southern Africa. A partnership between mobile phone provider Orange Botswana and Small House Records/Mud Hut Studios ensures that musicians get a slice of the profit pie. Managing Director Solomon Monyame of Small House Records has signed a contract with Orange to share the profits from ring tone and song downloads to mobile phone subscribers. With more than 76.8 million people currently subscribing to mobile phone services in Africa, and the number growing by about 58 per cent each year for the last five years, the potential royalties market for African musicians is vast if this initiative is replicated across the continent. – (January 2007)

Bolivian Film School's Film Scene Paying Off

A film school in Bolivia shows how a creative hub can become the start of something much bigger. The school is inspiring a new generation of young people to get into filmmaking, and one of its lecturers is already experiencing global success acting in an award-winning Spanish film.

Bolivia's economy has grown over the last decade, and the country is beginning to shed its long-standing reputation for grinding poverty and political instability. Public spending has risen, and more money has been put into programmes to reduce poverty. More students are entering higher education and the country recognizes an urgent need for greater awareness and understanding of modern technology.

Film and media production have been targeted as an important way to advance Bolivia's social and economic development.

Veteran Bolivian filmmaker Jorge Sanjines has been one of the most passionate exponents of using film to spread the stories and wisdom of Bolivia's indigenous people. He believes that their stories show an understanding of the need to balance the demands of humanity with preservation of the environment. Film, to him, is a way to liberate Bolivian society and address its pervasive problems of poverty, hunger and marginalization.

This agrees with rising global awareness of the importance of the creative economy in future development. No longer seen as a frippery, the creative economy is the "interface between creativity, culture, economics and technology" (UNCTAD). It is seen as a way for emerging economies to leapfrog into high-growth areas in the world economy.

In the Bolivian city of El Alto, the **Cine Alto** film school at the **Municipal Arts School of El Alto** offers students a free education in filmmaking. Lecturer and actor **Juan Carlos Aduviri** is one of the high-profile successes to come from the school since it opened in 2006.

A graduate of the school and a lecturer on screenwriting, he got a big career boost by acting in the award-winning Spanish film, "Even the Rain", receiving a Best Newcomer nomination at Spain's top film awards, the Goyas.

The film is set in the Bolivian city of Cochabamba, where protests a decade ago broke out over privatization of water services. It stars well-known Mexican actor Gael Garcia Bernal, who plays a filmmaker set on making a movie about the Spanish conquest of the Americas. While making the film, the so-called "water wars" break out and the actor played by Aduviri must balance his film role with being a protest leader.

The protests against water privatization in Cochabamba led to the election of Evo Morales as Bolivia's president in December 2005.

Cine Alto is one of four film schools in Bolivia but the only one that does not charge students tuition. Cash is tight for the school, which is a simple place that runs on thin resources. The classrooms have bare walls and broken windows, but the school is serious about transforming the lives of young people. The curriculum emphasizes a strong theoretical foundation in combination with technical and practical training.

"Conditions in Bolivia to make a film are challenging and in El Alto, it's even more difficult", Aduviri told the BBC.

"Life is hard here in El Alto, and this film school is trying to rescue this talent and support these young people."
– (March 2011)

•**European Film Festival in Bolivia:**

Website: cineeuropeobolivia.org

•**Cine Alto on Facebook:**

Website: es-la.facebook.com/cine.alto

•**AltoTV:** A non-profit television documentary-making project that has made small films on El Alto.

Website: altotvgerman.blogspot.com

•**The Public University of El Alto:** **Website:** enlaupea.com

•A course on Bolivian filmmaking taught by award-winning filmmaker Ismael Saavedera.

Website: sit.edu/studyabroad/sss_blv.cfm

Filmmaking resources

Technology has revolutionized visual media. The development of small, handheld digital devices – such as the Flip (support.theflip.com/en-uk/home) – and the inclusion of video capability on mobile phones and portable devices have quickly placed in the hands of people a powerful means to make small films. On top of this movie-making capability, it is now very easy to then broadcast and share films with people around the world. With many video-sharing sites available on the Internet and mobile phones, knowledge-sharing about development is now close to people and not just in the hands of professional filmmakers. It is now possible to record more or less in real time a project's progress and seek feedback.

Go to Contacts and Resources at the back of the magazine for links (page 56).

Photo Credits: Cine Alto

Local Animation: A Way Out of Poverty

One of the more remarkable creative developments since 2000 has been the explosion in animation production in the developing world, in particular Asia. Once seen as frivolous or unnecessary, animation is now acknowledged as a high-growth area and a critical component in the emerging economies being shaped by information technology.

The demand for more animation is being fuelled by several trends. Lucrative outsourcing contracts with major global film studios such as Walt Disney and Warner Brothers get much of the attention. But even more importantly for small entrepreneurs, the rapid growth of information technology and mobile phones is fuelling demand for animation with a local flavour, which is an excellent way to make applications more attractive to users. As computers and animation software become cheaper, it is easier for entrepreneurs to compete with the bigger studios. It all started with the popularity of Japanese anime animation, which kicked the door open in the West, sparking an appetite for fresh, new styles unseen before.

The animation leaders in Asia are Japan, the Philippines, the Republic of Korea and Taiwan Province of China, with India rising quickly. Since animation production is very lucrative and a labour-intensive business (labour accounts for 70 to 80 per cent of business costs), other Asian countries such as China, Malaysia, Singapore and Vietnam have recently started their own industries.

India's National Association of Software and Service Companies (NASSCOM) has forecast that the Indian animation sector will have a turnover of US \$950 million in 2009, while its gaming industry will reach US \$300 million (from US \$30 million in 2005). The global industry is huge: it is estimated that games will gross US \$11 billion and animation US \$35 billion by 2009. China was able to make US \$604 million in 2005. The Animation World Network's (AWN) Animation Industry Database lists 48 studios operating in the Philippines alone. Even in Africa, there have been attempts to get things going.

In 2004, the Government of China set up four animation schools to increase its overall animation programming from 5,000 hours a year to 16,700 hours a year: **Communication University of China, Beijing Film Academy, China Academy of Art, and Tianjin Sorun Digital Media School**. More than 200 animated films were produced in 2004.

Indian animation feature productions have exploded in the past few years. In 2005, animated feature **Jai Hanuman** started the current boom. Its quality marked a departure from past Indian productions and heralded a new era. Importantly, it out-grossed any Disney film in India and proved films

Some images from Epiphany Films' many productions

featuring local topics could be commercially successful. It is a difficult market, with 14 official languages and 1,400 dialects. At present, the huge Indian market has little locally produced animation to feed its needs, but by 2007, 71 Indian animation films were announced to be in production.

Productions in development draw heavily on India's culture and love of gods. They include **Epiphany Films' The Dream Blanket**, a Tibetan fairy tale, and **Graphiti Studios' Action Hero BC**, a teenager who fights evil.

The world's animation producers scour India for talent to outsource. Global films with some Indian production in them include "Finding Nemo", "The Lion King" and "The Adventures of Tenali Raman". **Toonz Animation Studio** based at the **Technopark** in Kerala, was called by **Animation Magazine** one of the top ten studios in the world.

In Africa, South Africa has by far the most dynamic and sophisticated animation sector. Ten years after the birth of democracy, hundreds of production companies and several 2D animation houses have been established. South Africa advertises itself as a less costly place to produce animation than

more established animation countries.

The highly successful South African 3D animated series **Magic Cellar** by Johannesburg's **Morula Pictures** – the first of its kind based on African culture – was successfully sold to the US Home Box Office channel in 2006. Based on 20 folk tales, the stories were collected through interviews with elders in African villages. **Mfundu Vundla**, 58, who owns Morula, South Africa's largest black-led studio, said his productions are meant to counter the perception of "Africans as unsophisticated, superstitious idiots who visited witch doctors to solve problems". It employs 60 people and dozens of actors.

Moustapha Alassane of Niger, one of Africa's film pioneers, said: "The good thing about animation is that you can do it on a shoestring budget. With the computer, animation is getting easier and anyone can do it now. I want to encourage young Africans to use new technologies for animation." – (December 2007)

• **AnimationSA.org**: The South African Animation Directory: The official website for the South African animation industry, it hosts lots of information on jobs, training, events and developments.
Website: animationsa.org

Old Adage Gets New Life

The self-sufficient schools in action

Education is critical for development and improving people's lives. Universal primary education is a Millennium Development Goal and countries are now allocating more funds for primary education across the global South. However, the options available to youth after primary education are often very limited.

The World Bank estimates that only 9 per cent of youth in the developing world will be able to go to a university or benefit from higher education scholarships. For the vast majority, getting a job is often the only viable option to securing a livelihood but in most developing countries, the number of formal-sector jobs is low and the only option is self-employment. Acquiring relevant training and practical skills can be crucial to becoming successfully self-employed. But where will the training and skills come from and who will provide the training and pay for it?

This dilemma is being addressed by the "self-sufficient schools" concept. The model combines entrepreneurship and vocational education through school-based businesses that blend training and revenue-generation. The principle is simple: entrepreneurship and business skills are taught by successful entrepreneurs.

The model is being pioneered in several countries and has been successfully applied by United Kingdom-based charity **Teach a Man to Fish** in Ghana and Paraguay, targeting rural youth from farming families through a network of 250 vocational experts and

institutions in 45 countries. The approach promotes a model for making education both more relevant and financially sustainable in rural communities.

Self-sufficient schools share several characteristics: they produce and sell goods and services; they focus on developing an entrepreneurial culture; they make a direct connection between theory, practical work and financial reward; they encourage learning by doing; and they strive to keep improving in order to remain economically competitive. Students are encouraged to work cooperatively and receive support after graduating, often in the form of microfinance for their new businesses.

In the South American country of Paraguay, one of Teach a Man to Fish's partners is **Fundacion Paraguaya – San Francisco Agricultural High School** – run by an NGO committed to poverty reduction through supporting entrepreneurship – found that small-scale farmers not only knew how to produce food but also how to make a prosperous living out of it when given the right tools. Taking over a school previously run by a religious order, the NGO had the opportunity to put the concept to the test.

Quick Facts

- The **Teach A Man To Fish** network now has 2,500 members from 125 countries;
- The **San Francisco Agricultural School in Paraguay** reached self-sufficiency in 2007 and has been 100 per cent self-sufficient for five years, generating US \$ 300,000 a year through educational income-generating projects run by teachers and students;
- A movement has sprung up in different countries of the world to promote this 100 per cent community-based curriculum that almost guarantees 100 per cent employability of the schools' graduates;
- Fundacion Paraguaya has opened an office in the United Republic of Tanzania to set up a training center for Africa and to establish five self-sufficient schools in the country.

Source: Martin Burt, Director Ejecutivo, Fundacion Paraguaya, Executive Director, Teach A Man To Fish.

fundacionparaguaya.org.py
teachamantofish.org.uk
educationthatpaysforitself.org.uk

"It is not a matter of knowing how to grow the crop or raise the animal; it is a matter of how to make money and then how to be financially successful doing farming in poor countries", said the organization's head, Martin Burt.

The Paraguayan school is half way through its five-year plan and already is covering two thirds of its recurring costs from the production and sale of goods and services, including specialist cheeses.
 – (May 2007)

• **Teach a Man to Fish: Education that Pays for Itself:** **Website:** teachamantofish.org.uk
 • **Fundacion Paraguaya – San Francisco Agricultural High School:** **Website:** fundacionparaguaya.org.py

Cambodian Bloggers Champion New, Open Ways

The Southeast Asian country of Cambodia has had a very difficult time over the past few decades. In the 1950s and 1960s, it was seen as a glamorous and vibrant place. Dynamic, ambitious and newly independent from French colonial rule, Cambodia embarked on an extensive programme of building that is now called “New Khmer Architecture”. It is the most visible legacy of this modernizing time.

But with the war in nearby Vietnam worsening in the 1970s, the destabilizing effect of the conflict gave rise to the Khmer Rouge, a radical and genocidal movement under dictator Pol Pot that killed an estimated 2 million Cambodians. It came to an end when newly independent Vietnam invaded the country to overturn the Khmer Rouge regime and end the genocide that had raged between 1975 and 1979.

By the early 1990s, the United Nations was helping Cambodia to make the transition to democracy and redevelop its economy after the trauma of the Khmer Rouge years.

Today’s Cambodia is a country with a fast-growing economy – at 5.5 per cent in 2010 according to Prime Minister Hun Sen – but still trying to come to grips with the pain and damage of the Khmer Rouge period.

On the Internet, pioneering bloggers are trying to bridge the gap between reluctance to speak out about those years and the need for the country to modernize and open up. In the past, keeping quiet in public was the best survival strategy and outspoken voices could end up silenced forever.

The Internet is still in its infancy in Cambodia, with only 78,000 users in 2010 (Internet World Stats) – up from 6,000 in 2000 but still tiny in a population of 14,805,358 (World Bank). Cambodia still has high levels of poverty and an illiteracy rate of 26 per cent (ILO), leaving access to the Internet and computers a minority pursuit.

The first connections to the Internet in Cambodia were set up in 1994 and Internet cafés have been flourishing since the mid-2000s.

One role model can be found at the **Blue Lady Blog**. Its author, **Kounila Keo**, blogs about her daily frustrations, passions, and life as a young woman who has been working as a newspaper journalist. Her blog tackles anything Cambodian, from education and politics to lifestyle, press freedom, culture and problems facing the country. She is a passionate explainer of Cambodia’s blogging culture.

She started the Blue Lady Blog in 2007 and in a talk at Phnom Penh’s TEDx in February described how blogging had transformed her life in three ways:

- (1) Freedom of speech: She could now fully express herself and venture opinions she could not do even as a journalist.
- (2) Self-education and self esteem: she has had to learn things on her own, which in turn has boosted her confidence.

“Cloggers” gathered to support one another

Kounila Keo, author of **Blue Lady Blog** and a Cambodian “Clogger”

(3) Knowledge and new perspectives: blogging connects her with people around the world with whom she would not normally have contact. Also blogging is becoming the new voice of a new generation of youth, enabling them to redefine the country’s development challenges in their own terms.

Keo found that blogging altered the challenges facing youth, raising the question “What can young Cambodians do for Cambodia?” She believes Cambodian youth should do something rather than wait for opportunities to come to them. Young people have told her that her blog has spurred them into action. – (March 2011)

- **Cloggers scene:** A presentation about the Cloggers Scene and how it works. **Website:** slideshare.net/kalyankeo/cloggers-life-an-introduction-to-cambodian-blogosphere
- **Afrinnovator:** Is about telling the stories of African start-ups, African innovation, African-made technology, and African tech entrepreneurship and entrepreneurs. **Website:** afrinnovator.com

Turning African Youth On to Technology

An African NGO believes that the Internet is the single biggest key to rapid development in Africa, and it is working to connect youth, women and rural populations to the web and, in turn, switch them on to the vast resources stored across the world's Internet sites.

After initial successes with a youth project and with farmers, **Voices of Africa** (VOA) (voicesofafrica.info) is now seeking to scale up its work to fan out across Africa – and take its services to the world's largest refugee camp, the Dadaab Refugee Camp in Kenya.

The youth and technology empowerment NGO has developed a business model to deliver low-cost Internet access and e-resources to Africa's slums and rural farmers.

VOA argues that “the digital divide, defined by a lack of access to information for a specific population, symbolizes the largest difference between developed and developing countries: the opportunity to obtain and utilize information”.

“The digital divide runs much deeper than hardware and software”, it says. “While equipment is necessary, it is not sufficient. The real heart of the digital divide is that those without access to information resources often suffer needlessly while the solutions to their problems are floating in the air.”

But why is the Internet so important?

“The Internet puts the choice of content at the fingertips of the user”, explains executive director **Crystal Kigoni**. “Traditional media is one-way communications. Internet is bidirectional.

“Our NGO is completely grass roots. We train the people who train the people. It is an each one, teach one philosophy and is highly effective. We also design our projects to be self-sustainable after one year of successful implementation.”

The philosophy behind Voices of Africa – sustainable development through information empowerment – is to give people the information and resources to take better control of their lives.

Access to the Internet in Africa is patchy and, for the poor, an expensive resource. The penetration of mobile phones in Africa has been spectacular in the past five

years but there are limits to the resources people can afford to access with their phones. Issues about data costs, mobile phone networks, and mobile phone capability.

VOA targets youth and women in sub-Saharan Africa through online educational resources offered on its e-learning website (elearning.voicesofafrica.info). The resources have been certified by Nazarene University (anu.ac.ke), a private university in Nairobi, Kenya.

The e-learning resources include high-quality training videos, presentations and screencasts. Like a movie, it is a digital recording of changes on a computer screen and is used to teach software – to share on the web. The resources are also shared through compact discs (CDs) and iPods.

Project coordinator **Nick Kungu** coordinates the staff working on the pilot Kenyan projects: a rural Internet kiosk; a youth empowerment centre; and **KiberaNet**, which launched in August 2011. VOA uses a part-time and volunteer staff of more than 20 Kenyans and four international “virtual” volunteers.

The group is also working with farmers in Kutus, central Kenya, to help them get a better price for their products and introduce sustainable agricultural practices. This is done through online courses so that the farmers do not need to travel. It is hoped they can improve the supply of food for the country.
– (August 2011)

• **The Impact of Mobile Phones on Profits from Livestock Activities** by Roxana Barrantes. **Website:** mendeley.com/research/impact-mobile-phones-profits-livestock-activities-evidence-puno-peru-14
• **2011 UNHCR Country Operations Profile – Kenya.** **Website:** unhcr.org/cgi-bin/texis/vtx/page?page=49e483a16

Innovative initiatives such as Kenya's **Kuweni Serious** (above) are reaching out to youth to teach new skills. Kuweni Serious is running a training course for girls aged over eight years in some of the poorest parts of the capital, Nairobi.

Using a clever interactive learning toy called **Pico-Crickets**, manufactured by the Canadian **Playful Invention Company** (PICO), they place more emphasis on artistic expression. The company created the PicoCricket Kit as a way to integrate art and technology to “spark creative thinking in girls and boys eight years and older”, according to its website.

A typical kit includes a central PicoCricket that a child then plugs into various motors, sensors, lights and other devices to make something that can spin, light up or play music. It is intended to give free rein to both technological innovation and artistic expression.

Cashing In on Music in Brazil

Brazilian musicians have found a way to prosper and exploit the realities of music distribution in the modern age. The biggest problem for most artists – both beginners and those who are more established – is how to earn an income from their work. In the digital age, it is next to impossible to stop people from freely copying your music and passing it on.

The impact of digital technology on the global music business has been earth-shattering. It is estimated that 95 per cent of music digital downloads are unauthorized, with no payment to artists and producers. While the legal digital music business grew for the sixth consecutive year in 2008, with a 25 per cent increase in global sales to a trade value of US \$3.7 billion, this only makes up 20 per cent of total music sales (IFPI). Even legal digital services such as Apple's iTunes have suffered.

An economic solution to this conundrum is critical for the growth of creative economies in the South.

The traditional music industry model from the analogue age – where copies of music are tightly controlled and royalties and profits funnel back to recording companies – has become obsolete in the digital age. With digital recordings, it is easy to copy high-quality music and distribute it for free through the Internet, by audio music players such as the iPod or on discs.

Many are saying that a corner has been turned: free distribution is the new future and illegal copying is the new normal. The model for music making has been turned on its head: rather than high investment and high returns, it is now low investment and low returns.

Most Southern musicians will be familiar with this model – they are already living it. Emulating the champagne and jets lifestyle of the Rolling Stones or Beyonce is beyond the reality of most, but they can build a slower and more sustainable income with the new digital model.

A music phenomenon in Brazil's poorer neighbourhoods, *tecnobrega* (*brega* means "cheesy" or "corny") is a mix of electronic beats from the 1980s, mixed with found snippets of strange sounds or sound bites, combined in a so-called "mash-up". It makes for an easy-to-dance-to mix.

"Tecnobrega is a regional music, the music that people here in (the State of) Para most enjoy", **DJ Edilson** told the BBC. "The secrets are the beats which drive people crazy."

With music becoming easier and less costly to record to a high standard, and distribution of music less and less a money-making opportunity, musicians have turned to economic models revolving around live performance to earn the bulk of their income.

"What is going on is that people, sometimes in very poor areas, are appropriating electronic instruments like computers and synthesizers to create their own music", said **Ronaldo Lemos**, a professor at the respected **Getulio Vargas Foundation** and project lead for the **Creative Commons Brazil**.

"So this is a phenomenon that is going on not only in the *tecnobrega* scene but with many

scenes around the world like Kuduro in Angola, Kwaito in South Africa, Bubblin' in Suriname."

The *tecnobrega* model works like this: People set up makeshift studios in their homes. They use a personal computer and a software programme to mix and blend the songs. Once the songs are ready, they either organize themselves or, more often, perform at a sound system party. There are said to be as many as 4,000 sound system parties per month in Belem, Brazil, and it is a hugely competitive market. The sound system parties can vary from a small crowd to heaving groups of 15,000 people. – (March 2009)

• **Tecnobrega**: A documentary trailer for a film about *tecnobrega* in Brazil directed by Gustavo Godinho e Vladimir Cunha.
Website: vimeo.com/1993239

Bringing the Invention and Innovation Mindset to Young Kenyans

A highly innovative new way to teach the basics of electronics, computing and technological innovation is being pioneered in the slums of Nairobi, Kenya. Driven by the desire to counter perceptions of apathy among young people, NGO **Kuweni Serious** is running a training course for girls over eight years of age in some of the poorest parts of the city to turn on a new generation to the power of technology to make change.

“Technology is pivotal in our work, as Kuweni Serious is a primarily online platform that seeks to create offline action”, according to Kuweni Serious’ **Rachel Gichengo**. “It’s positive in that you can reach a lot of people with solid messages that are in bite-size pieces that are easy to disseminate and consume. Everyone can pass on the information with a simple click. It’s an easier way to begin socio-political discussion among people who would otherwise not be drawn into these kinds of discussions because they’re not presented in a way that appeals to them. The typical profile of a KS volunteer is someone in their 20s, middle-class, has some experience volunteering, has never been to a slum despite living in Nairobi, but wants more for their country.”

The course uses a clever, hands-on approach to teaching. Instructors use a new generation of learning toys that help young people to understand how technology works and gives

them their first taste of what it is like to build something from scratch. These toys comprise various components that perform tasks – a light, a motor, a computer, a music player. Active invention is required to work out how to assemble these parts to make something bigger and better. This stands in stark contrast to toys – or computer games – where all the hard work is done for the child and they just have to play.

“We chose tech training because it’s a traditionally underrepresented area when it comes to reaching this particular group (underprivileged girls), yet such an important set of skills to be taught in this day and age”, confirms Gichengo. “We want to expand these girls’ thinking, to get them interested in the possibilities of careers in science and tech, rather than perpetuate the idea that all they’ll ever do, based on their circumstances, is tailoring or dance. We hoped to open our girls’ worlds a bit as well as link them to our Kuweni Serious community of volunteers.”

Called **PicoCrickets** and manufactured by the **Canadian Playful Invention Company (PICO)**, the toys were developed from research and ideas at the Lifelong Kindergarten group at the **MIT (Massachusetts Institute of Technology) Media Lab**.

“Pico Crickets are cool”, continues Gichengo. “They’re a fun way to learn to build things, to learn the connection between hardware and software, to begin to understand what computers can do. They make learning easy, and they make science seem accessible to a group that tends to see it as too hard for them. The kits were paid for by a grant from the Girl Effect.”

The MIT lab conducted intensive research into creative learning environments for children. One of the first fruits of this research was Lego Mindstorms, kits that enable children to make and programme their own robots. →

A typical kit (above) includes a central PicoCricket that a child then plugs into various motors, sensors, lights and other devices to make something that can spin, light up or play music. It is intended to give free rein to both technological innovation and artistic expression.

Inspired by this work, the PicoCricket places more emphasis on artistic expression. The company created the Pico-Cricket Kit as a way to integrate art and technology to “spark creative thinking in girls and boys 8 years and older”, according to its website.

A typical kit includes a central Pico-Cricket that a child then plugs into various motors, sensors, lights and other devices to make something that can spin, light up or play music. It is intended to give free rein to both technological innovation and artistic expression.

Kenya experienced violent rioting during the 2007 and 2008 elections. The shock of the events produced a number of initiatives to counter the violence and the social and economic disruption that it has caused. One of the most well-known innovations, Ushahidi, a crisis-mapping platform, has been deployed around the world and led to many other new innovations.

Kuveni Serious is also a result of this crisis. The NGO sets out to counter the stereotype of Kenya’s youth as a “hedonistic generation of brand-obsessed youth, moving from party to party in the night and congregating on Facebook during the day”.

Kuveni Serious believes that young people in Kenya were shocked into action when violence broke out during the elections. Prices jumped for everything – from fuel to food – and water and power started to be rationed. It was a wake-up call to youth: it was becoming harder and harder to ignore what was happening in the country.

Kuveni Serious was founded by Kenyan youth and asked the question “how do Kenya’s youth feel about all the chaos around us?” It seeks to rally young people to their motto: “Fighting the evil forces of apathy”.

Their **125/100** programme set out to train 125 girls on a 100-day course. It ended with a graduation ceremony on 2 July 2011.

The programme, run by volunteers from the University of Nairobi, has taught basic computer skills, got the children working on Google Maps and making – and inventing – things using the PicoCricket.

The girls on the course came from Baba Dogo and Kibera, Nairobi’s largest slum.

The technology training programme lasted between three and six hours a week for 12 weeks. The inventions made by the children included merry-go-rounds, a lamp stand and fan, and miniature automobiles. Participants even came to grips with Google Maps and learned how to use mobile phones in citizen journalism. At the end of the course, all the children received a certificate reinforcing their sense of accomplishment and achievement.

“We hope to continue doing similar projects, scaling up 125/100, and working on developing a corps of everyday change makers among young, educated, middle class Kenyans”, according to Gichengo. – (July 2011)

•**Make Magazine:** “Make Magazine brings the do-it-yourself mindset to all the technology in your life. Make is loaded with exciting projects that help you make the most of your technology at home and away from home. We celebrate your right to tweak, hack, and bend any technology to your own will.”

Website: makezine.com

•**Lego Mindstorms Robot-making Kits:**

Website: mindstorms.lego.com/en-us/Default.aspx

•**Southern Innovator Issue 1:** New global magazine celebrating innovation across the global South.

Website: scribd.com/doc/57980406/Southern-Innovator-Issue-1

•**iHub Nairobi:** iHub Nairobi’s Innovation Hub for the technology community, is an open space for the technologists, investors, tech companies and hackers in the area. This space is a tech community facility with a focus on young entrepreneurs, web and mobile phone programmers, designers and researchers. It is part open community workspace (co-working), part vector for investors and venture capitalists and part incubator.

Website: ihub.co.ke/pages/home.php

•**Social Enterprise** (en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Social_enterprise): Learn more about the vibrant world of social enterprise and connect with others.

Website: socialenterpriselive.com

Turning Street Children into Entrepreneurs

The United Nations estimates that 500 million people around the world are homeless, and UNICEF estimates that India alone has 11 million homeless children on its streets (though it is difficult to pin down an exact figure). In order to survive another day, these children will work in one way or another.

Street and working children have money: it is a natural consequence of having to be resourceful to survive. But what they don’t have is access to banking services or trustworthy financial advice that can help them to gain wealth and move out of poverty and towards a brighter future.

The **Children’s Development Bank** in India is one initiative that seeks to turn these neglected children into the next generation of entrepreneurs. The Bank works on banking and cooperative principles, where savers are members and joint owners. Any child can save money with the Bank and earn interest, as well as take out loans if they are over 15 years old. It was started in 2001 and was inspired by the Youth Bank in the United Kingdom. Interest made by the Bank is shared by its members, as is the case with many cooperative banks and credit unions.

The Bank is managed jointly by children and adults. The children have a say in how the Bank is run and on what conditions it should lend money. They also keep an eye on borrowers to prevent them from running off without repaying loans.

For these vulnerable children, this model has many advantages: they can put money aside without fear of its being stolen or lost, save for important things such as clothes, or pay for their education.

A key part of the Bank’s mandate is helping the children to build entrepreneurial skills for business. The Bank has branches in Afghanistan, India and Sri Lanka.

Ten-year-old **Deepak Prahlad**, a street child in Delhi, dreams of being a doctor. “I know what it takes to be a doctor. I need to study hard and need to save a lot of money”, he told the *Hindustan Times*. For now, he works as a rag picker but has started saving 30 to 40 rupees a day in the Children’s Development Bank. The Bank has 1,300 members in the city and pays 3.5 per cent interest on savings accounts. – (November 2007)

•**Making Cents International:** “It inspires youth, practitioners, policy makers and funders to more effectively share and develop partnerships, programmes and policies that support youth entrepreneurs.” **Website:** makingcents.com

Urban Youth: A Great Source of Untapped Growth

The world's growing urbanization means that a whole generation of youth will have dramatically different lives than their parents. The world's 3.3 billion urbanites now outnumber rural residents for the first time (UNFPA's **State of the World Population 2007 Report**). And the vast majority live in slums or periurban areas, places of sprawl, where public services are poor and housing conditions unhealthy.

Most young people working in the urban informal sector live in slum areas: for example, 75 per cent in Benin in Africa, and 90 per cent in Burkina Faso, the Central African Republic, Chad and Ethiopia. Most of this work is just bare survival work: according to the International Labour Organization, approximately 85 per cent of all new employment falls into this category.

Getting youth into quality work and earning more than enough simply to survive is critical to building a healthy society. Young people are bombarded every day with good and bad influences, and, as UNFPA found in its *Growing Up Urban: Youth Supplement*, "the interactions with the urban environment can have an intense impact on the socialization of young people, exposing them to a multitude of influences as they develop, experiment, question, and assume roles in their societies".

It is predicted that over the next 10 years, 1.2 billion youth will enter the working-age population (UNFPA), but youth unemployment is a huge problem around the world: unemployed young people make up almost half (43.7 per cent) of the world's total unemployed (UNFPA). Young people ages 15 to 19 are more than three times as likely to be unemployed as adults. Young people are the future, a resource that no society can afford to waste. If their innate energy and enthusiasm are tapped, countries can see significant economic growth.

There are youth entrepreneurs who are defying the gloom and coming up with great business ideas. Five finalists for **BBC Swahili's**

The global innovation culture is finding its expression in many forms. American magazine *Make* is one example and so is *Southern Innovator* magazine.

regional entrepreneur competition – **Faidika na BBC** (Prosper with the BBC) – offer inspiration for youth across the South. Finalists from Burundi, Kenya, Rwanda, Uganda and the United Republic of Tanzania were selected for their bright schemes.

The overall winner for 2008 was 24-year-old Burundian student **Ashura Kisesa** for a plan to build commercial public toilets in the cities and towns of East and Central Africa. Kisesa has 12 brothers and sisters and is studying for a degree in agronomy at Burundi University.

"I am very happy to win the top prize in this competition", she told the BBC.

"The lack of public toilets throughout East and Central Africa is a major problem that needs to be addressed and I hope to make a difference with my business idea. My whole family wanted me to win and they really supported me, which makes me especially proud. I cannot wait to get started with my business."

Kisesa was awarded US \$5,000 to put towards her business.

Kenyan national winner, 22-year-old **Witness Omoga** from Kakamega, wants to make identity cards for schools. Right now he works as a volunteer at his uncle's photo studio and hopes to get into Makerere University to pursue a degree in computer science. "I am very excited", he said to the BBC. "I have never been number one in my life, but now I have emerged first in this competition." – (July 2008)

- **2008 Global Youth Enterprise Conference:** Designed as a participatory learning event, this conference aims to support youth enterprise and entrepreneurship programmes and policies to achieve greater effectiveness around the world.
Website: youthenterpriseconference.org
- **KickStart** is a South African project aimed at inculcating a culture of entrepreneurship among young people between the ages of 18 and 35, by promoting business awareness through training, providing grants as start-up capital and providing mentorship and assistance during the setting-up phase of the business.
Website: sabkickstart.co.za
- **iDISC – the infoDev Incubator Support Center** – is a virtual networking and knowledge-sharing platform for incubators and technology parks leveraging information and communication technology (ICT) to facilitate entrepreneurship and new business creation in developing countries.
Website: idisc.net/en/lnx.html

Being a Southern Innovator A Guide

In researching this issue of the magazine, we identified some common steps that help people to become successful Southern innovators. Get things right at the beginning, and you will increase your chances of success. Taking the time to think about the details of your initiative is a good way to prepare for the hard work ahead. Good luck!

These suggestions are by no means meant to be a substitute for good business advice (check out the resources throughout the magazine). They are just some common elements that we found in all the successful innovators in the stories.

Read the Money, Money section at the end of the magazine for ideas and tips on how to obtain funding for your venture. We did not cover money here as a separate step because we have found that it is just one aspect of the success story. In fact, getting the steps that we detail right will significantly increase your chances of the money finding you.

Step 1 Know thyself

Why are you doing this? Southern innovators show a great awareness of who they are and why they are doing what they do. They have thought about their “competitors”, what they do right and what they get wrong. What do you believe in? How would friends describe you? Do you like to work with others or are you better working on your own? The answers to these questions should inform how you present and build your venture.

1. Building a business model.
2. Designing your brand and logo.

Step 2 Designing success

Brand: The brand is something special: it should be something unique to you and your venture. A clear brand – the thing that people remember about you – does not have to cost much but it does have to be clear and understandable. Get this wrong, and you may repel more people than you attract. It is not about just having a nice logo and design: it is about integrity and how closely your actions match your words.

Look at how other businesses/products/services represent themselves. Who do you think is successful at getting attention and who is failing?

Once you have some answers to these questions, distil them into what your offering is to the marketplace and how you want to be seen. What emotional connection do you want to make with people?

Logo: A logo is a simple design tool to make sure that people remember who you are and understand what you are about at a quick glance.

Embed the culture of your brand: This is critical as you start to take on others to help with your venture, from family and friends to employees. Make sure that they understand the brand ethos of your venture and how this affects how they behave and present the venture and themselves.

Step 3 Building a team: Finding the right people

As you evolve past a one-person operation, the need to hire others and build a team will come up. Depending on your resources and circumstances, how much time can be dedicated to interviewing and training people will vary. By having a brand culture already in place, there will be an implicit understanding of how the venture functions and this will help in guiding new people to work in the right way for your enterprise.

Step 4 Managing your work: How are you going to get things done?

Designing your work process should evolve out of your circumstances and how to create your service or product in the most efficient way possible. Take time every day and every week to think about this and to constantly refine what you are doing. Pay attention to technological advances and to how competitors and others are changing with the times. Sketch out your work process on a piece of paper so that you can understand all the steps.

- 3. Building a team.
- 4. Company website.
- 5. Business card.
- 6. Managing your work flow.
- 7. Meeting the market.

Step 5 The launch: Meeting the marketplace

If the previous steps have been followed, then this will be a different prospect than if you just jumped in unprepared. As the Chinese strategist Sun Tzu once noted, all battles are won before they are fought. This insight shows the power of preparation.

Any new venture requires plenty of hard work and the ability to adapt to new circumstances. However, armed with a brand ethos, the pressures of day-to-day work will be easier to handle, and armed with a logo, people will begin to remember you among all the others.

MDGs (Millennium Development Goals)

Goal 1: Eradicate extreme poverty and hunger

Goal 2: Achieve universal primary education

Goal 3: Promote gender equality and empower women

Goal 4: Reduce child mortality

Goal 5: Improve maternal health

Goal 6: Combat HIV/AIDS, malaria and other diseases

Goal 7: Ensure environmental sustainability

Goal 8: Develop a global partnership for development

THE DEMOGRAPHIC DIVIDEND

6%: East Asia's growth years from 1965 to 1990 saw real per capita income grow 6 per cent per year. This was a result of its "demographic dividend", when the working-age population grew four times faster than the dependent population of non-working-age youth and elderly. A strong educational system and trade liberalization policies enabled national economies to absorb this "boom" generation into the workforce. The demographic dividend fuelled the region's spectacular economic boom and accounted for approximately one fourth to two fifths of this growth.

Source: Rand: Banking the "Demographic Dividend" – How Population Dynamics can Affect Economic Growth.

Sources for infographics: ILO, ILO Global Employment Trends for Youth: Special Issue on the Impact of the Global Economic Crisis On Youth, Mobile Youth Around The World, Youth Making it Happen (ILO), Flight Stats (www.flightstats.com), Global Entrepreneurship Monitor (www.gemconsortium.org).

Data compiled with the assistance of Ecolometrics. (www.ecolometrics.co.uk)

Youth Entrepreneurialism: The Stages

Pre-entrepreneurs: 15-19 years old. The formative stage.

Budding entrepreneurs: 20-25 years old. The growth stage, with some experience and capital. Youth often face challenges of being marginal, of having staying power and of building successful enterprises.

Emergent entrepreneurs: 26-29 years old. They have a higher level of maturity and a greater chance of success.

Source: Youth Making It Happen (ILO)

POLICY RECOMMENDATIONS

- (1) Develop an integrated strategy for growth and job creation to ensure long-term, sustained and concerted action for the promotion of decent work for young people.
- (2) Establish broad-based partnerships to turn youth employment commitment into reality.
- (3) Improve the quality of jobs and the competitiveness of enterprises.
- (4) Invest in the quality of education and training and improve their relevance to labour-market needs.
- (5) Enhance the design and increase the funding of active labour-market policies to support the implementation of national youth employment priorities.
- (6) Review the provision of employment services, with the objective of offering a set of standard services to all young people and more intensive assistance to disadvantaged youth.
- (7) Pursue financial and macroeconomic policies that aim to remove obstacles to economic recovery.

Source: ILO

ENTREPRENEUR: DEFINITION

A person who sets up a business or businesses, taking on financial risks in the hope of profit.

Origin:

Early 19th century (denoting the director of a musical institution): from French, from *entreprendre* "undertake".

Source: Oxford Dictionary

BENEFITS OF YOUTH ENTREPRENEURIALISM

- Bringing alienated and marginalized youth back into the economic mainstream and giving them a sense of meaning and belonging.
- Helping to address some of the socio-psychological problems and delinquency that arise from joblessness.
- Helping youth to develop new skills and experiences that can then be applied to other challenges in life.
- Promoting innovation and resilience in youth.
- Promoting the revitalization of the local community by providing valuable goods and services.
- Capitalizing on the fact that young entrepreneurs may be particularly responsive to new economic opportunities and trends.

Source: Francis Chigunta (2002)

COMMON PROBLEMS EXPERIENCED BY YOUNG ENTREPRENEURS

BIGGEST OBSTACLES TO GETTING START-UP FUNDS

Lack of personal savings and resources

Lack of securities and credibility (for debt financing)

Lack of business experience and skills (for debt financing)

Strict credit-scoring methodologies and regulations

Complex documentation procedures

Long waiting periods (time needed to decide on an application for funding)

Lack of knowledge, understanding, awareness of start-up financing possibilities

Unfavourable firm characteristics and industry

Legal status/form of enterprise

Lack of (successful) micro-lending/finance and seed funding

Source: Young Entrepreneurs: Tomorrow's Business Leaders, Barclays Bank

Entrepreneurship

Introduction

While ideas about entrepreneurship vary widely from country to country and culture to culture, an economy that makes space for entrepreneurship and has a sophisticated understanding of how it can work to raise national wealth and meet development goals can reap huge benefits.

Entrepreneurship that is transparent and based on adding value to business activities or providing services and goods that people need and want can be a great way to boost incomes and meet social and development goals. Where existing methods and approaches are failing, entrepreneurs can break bad patterns and introduce new ways of doing things.

The stories in this issue of **Southern Innovator** offer some good examples of how entrepreneurship can reduce poverty and raise incomes in poor communities and countries. They also show that innovators are looking at current economic activities in new ways and in turn increasing incomes. They are also picking up on big trends - such as the move to urban areas or the rapid take-up of mobile phones - and seeing multiple business opportunities arising from them. And, interestingly, many of these pioneering innovators are women.

The stand-out country in the global South over the past 10 years has been China. It is a country packed with entrepreneurs, where more than 500 million people were lifted out of poverty in just 30 years and China became the world leader in South-South trade. Much of this has been the result of the hard work of entrepreneurs and business pioneers. All of this business activity has also put the country on course to become the world's largest economy. So, read on and take another look at what entrepreneurs can do to help in reaching development goals.

Made in Nigeria Works

Nigerian shoe and garment maker **Fut Conceptus** has been taking raw Nigerian leather that was once just sent overseas for export and instead is turning out high-quality shoes and bags made in Nigerian factories. These shoes – made in African, Spanish and Italian styles – meet international standards and are exported around Africa. The company has also established operations in Spain and the United Kingdom.

Started in 2008, the company got off to a good start by seeking out the best expertise to train its staff. Shoe-making experts from Spain were brought in to do the training. The company also imported top-quality machinery from Italy and Spain to make sure that its operations were modern and efficient.

Founder **Olumide Wole-Madariola** is proud of the achievement. “Nobody was ready for what we were doing... Nobody was ready for ‘Made in Nigeria’”, he told the *Wall Street Journal*.

futconceptus.com
– (December 2011)

Cities Are Where the Action Is

At the start of the 21st century, the world is undergoing a massive shift away from rural areas to cities. It is entering a new urban age and will need entrepreneurs, innovators and pioneers to make this an opportunity to improve the human condition rather than to make it worse. It will be up to the people of the global South to determine what future lays ahead.

95% global population growth in cities (2010-2020)

Source: UN-HABITAT

82.5% global population growth in cities located in developing countries (2010-2020)

75% of world population living in cities by 2050

Source: The Urban Age Project

Quick Facts

- China’s spending on research and development has risen an average of 20 per cent a year since 1999.
- India’s knowledge-based industries were a US \$57 billion export industry in 2007.
- 98 per cent of small and medium-sized enterprises in 14 African countries were using mobile phones by 2006.
- Estimated amount to provide micro-lending services to the world’s poor: US \$50 billion to US \$60 billion.
- Growth of mobile phone usage per year in Nigeria as of 2008: 25 per cent.
- Percentage of rural women market traders who thought that mobile phones had a big impact on their business: 95 per cent.

Q&A

(PULS) or Pakistan Urban Link and Support is an innovative mobile phone-based service directly connecting Pakistan’s employers with employees, bypassing middle-men and taking away the fee charged to the unemployed using existing employment services. Southern Innovator interviewed its founder, Asim Fayaz.

SI How will this service economically benefit the informal-sector workforce and how will it be able to boost their incomes?

Conventionally, the informal-sector workforce has found employment primarily through personal connections. In cases where that doesn’t work, they approach employment agencies and get enlisted. These employment agencies, behaving as middle-men, charge both the employer and the employee upon making a connection. PULS removes the need for the middle-man. Employees sign up on this platform themselves. Employers will only be charged a very small amount if they wish to contact a listed employee. If the employee is actually hired, PULS does not find out about the transaction and does not make anything off it.

SI And finally, what advice would you have for others trying to establish mobile phone platforms and services for low-income markets? What should they consider before starting a business/service?

Setting up the technology is just one part of the picture. You should identify a problem, look at how it’s currently being addressed, see how you can improve, research on how its being addressed in similar circumstances elsewhere (in our case, India works best), design your solution with just the main use cases addressed, and aggressively roll out. You should remember that you have to make revenue at some point but don’t let it be a hurdle in the short term.

Asim Fayaz
Pakistan Urban Link and Support, or PULS puls.pk
Curator
TEDxLahore
Website: tedxlahore.com
Twitter: [@TEDxLahore](https://twitter.com/TEDxLahore)

Photo Credit: Madécasse Chocolate Co.

Madagascar: Gourmet Chocolate

On the African island of Madagascar, a company is trying to reverse the practice of exporting Africa’s cocoa beans for manufacturing into products. **Madecasse Chocolate LLC** is a collaboration between American entrepreneur **Tim McCollum** and Madagascan chocolatier **Shahin Cassam Chenai**. The company is making a range of chocolate and vanilla products for US supermarkets.

madecasse.com
– (December 2011)

Innovation from the Global South

A major study has documented a rising tide of scientific innovation coming from Asia's fast-developing countries, especially China and India. Conducted over 18 months by United Kingdom-based think tank Demos, it challenges the conventional wisdom that scientific ideas come from the top universities and research laboratories of large companies based in Europe or the United States. It found ideas emerging in unexpected places, flowing around the world conveyed by a mobile diaspora of knowledge workers from the South.

China has seen its spending on research and development jump by 20 per cent each year since 1999. India is now producing 260,000 engineers a year and its number of engineering colleges is due to double to 1,000 by 2010. Research and development in India has grown threefold over the past decade. There is now a global flow of research and development money to the new knowledge centers of Bangalore, Beijing, Hyderabad and Shanghai.

The study found that the greater political and economic emphasis being placed on science and technology was

paying dividends. These emerging science powers are now investing heavily in research to become world leaders in information technology, biotechnology and nanotechnology within the next 10 to 15 years. This is also producing a flood of scientific papers from China and India to the world's prestigious scientific journals.

India's knowledge-based industries were a US \$57 billion export industry by the end of 2007, accounting for 4 million jobs and 7 per cent of Indian GDP. Interestingly, the study also found that a new wave of change is under way. Where once it was mostly low-wage manufacturing and call-center jobs that were going to China and India, a new wave of research and development jobs is now moving there.

Drawn in by technology clusters in Bangalore and Shanghai, "Microsoft began to realize we can't find all the talented people in the U.S. Nowhere in this universe has a higher concentration of IQ power (than India)", said **Harry Shun**, head of Microsoft's research in Asia. – (April 2007)

Dynamic Growth in African ICT Is Unlocking Secrets of SME Treasure Trove

A newly released survey of 14 African countries in 2006 documented the impact of information and communication technology (ICT) on private sector development and how it is contributing to developing a vibrant small and medium-sized enterprise (SME) sector in Africa. It discovered how dynamic the SME sector is, how it has rapidly adopted mobile phone technology (96 per cent have it), and how, if used properly in concert with this new technology, extraordinary economic growth is possible.

The survey – **Towards An African e-Index: SME e-Access and Usage in 14 African Countries** – covered only businesses employing fewer than 50 people and took in the vast informal sector in the countries. It investigated whether or not they had access to ICTs, how they were using them and if it was making them more productive. SMEs were especially interesting because they do not waste money (most people are just trying to survive) and they use only what is really useful to them to increase income. In the informal sector, this has become the mobile phone.

The countries surveyed included Botswana, Cameroon, Ethiopia, Ghana, Kenya, Mozambique, Namibia, Nigeria, Rwanda, South Africa, Uganda, the United Republic of Tanzania, Zambia and Zimbabwe. With most of the continent's poor working in the SME sector, little was actually known about the impact of ICT and its link to profitability and labour productivity. Also, surveying only formal businesses would be telling half the story since about two thirds of non-resource-driven GDP generation is derived from SMEs, and a large share of that from informal ones.

"This is a sector that has no access to formal finance", said **Dr. Christopher Stork**, a senior researcher at the Witwatersrand University in South Africa. "The mobile phones present an opportunity to tap into this market and offer finance, banking services, cash

transfers – we see this already in Kenya – without the risks of other services. These informal businesses can build up a history, learn how to better control their businesses, and receive loans. Where the financial system is dysfunctional or overpriced, airtime credits can be the new cash form."

Africa has a high proportion of entrepreneurs because people have next to no social supports to fall back on and need to do business to survive. Most fall into the informal sector, where they can avoid paying taxes, pay low wages, and keep overheads down. According to Stork, if governments are serious about dealing with poverty, then the best approach is to acknowledge this sector and rather than crush it, draw it in to become more sophisticated and efficient. He sees the mobile phones as key to this strategy.

"Innovative technology can help these entrepreneurs to acquire the tools they need to do business better. There is a lack of skills in all areas, a lack of accounting skills, a lack of basic financial management. This is where ICT can overcome this. SMEs can get a monthly statement with all their business transactions, making it easier to manage things. This would be a great way to distribute micro-finance. Savings clubs could store cash on the phones."

The e-Index also noted the trend for mobile phone providers to consolidate and offer common regional services. This could fuel an explosion in cross-border trade as it becomes less costly and easier to communicate via mobile phone for business. The e-Index also found the ever-growing importance of Internet cafés remains. They continue to evolve into multi-purpose business centers offering a wide range of services, from post to word-processing. At present, they still remain the main means of accessing the

Online Resources for SMEs

Start-ups and SMEs (small and medium-sized enterprises) are necessary for both economic growth and meeting the pressing needs of the growing populations across the global South. As experience has shown, it is start-ups and SMEs that bring new inventions and innovations to the marketplace. By being quick to adopt new technologies (often because they are seeking out the least costly and most efficient way to do something), they increase economic growth by their better use of technology. Think of how quickly market traders have adopted mobile phones as a tool to trade.

Here are some good starting points for anyone looking to start something.

West Africa Trade Hub:
Website: watradehub.com

SME Toolkit Kenya: **Website:**
kenya.smetoolkit.org/kenya/en

HSBC Knowledge Center:
News and Know-how for Your Business:
Website: knowledge.hsbc.co.uk

Internet, and with broadband still minimal and very expensive, it falls on mobile phones to offer Internet access, though this will remain mainly in the continent's capitals.

The survey's sponsor, **Research ICT Africa! (RIA!)** network, seeks to build an African knowledge base in support of ICT policy and regulatory design. The network emerged out of a growing need for hard data and analysis to help the continent to join the information age. Throughout 2007, it is conducting household surveys on e-access and e-usage and will present the findings in 2008. – (February 2007)

Social Franchising Models Proving Poor Bring Profits

The 4 billion people in the world who live on less than US \$2 a day have been described as the bottom of the economic pyramid, or BOP. In his book, **The Fortune at the Bottom of the Pyramid**, Indian business consultant and professor **C.K. Prahalad** argues that the developed world's approach to the world's majority must be turned on its head: rather than seeing the poor as a burden, worthy only of charity, Prahalad sees nothing but opportunity and unmet needs that business can address. In short, he argues, profits can be married with the goal of eradicating poverty.

Prahalad claims that the BOP is a market potentially worth US \$13 trillion, while the World Resources Institute puts it at US \$5 trillion in its latest report, **The Next 4 Billion**.

The challenge is to reach this vast market. One tool increasingly being used by business is social franchising. The concept borrows from the business world and the highly successful franchise models associated with fast-food restaurants and computer and clothing retailers – wherever rapid expansion and scaling up are required to reach the biggest market possible – and there is no bigger market, social franchising advocates claim, than the world's 4 billion poorest people.

In the past, most formal business in developing countries chased the small middle class or the even smaller elite or foreign expatriate communities. Traditional poverty eradication strategies have also been criticized for being too narrow, focused on a very small group, or for wasting time and resources replicating what has already been achieved elsewhere and for ballooning and shrinking depending on aid grants or success at fundraising. Social franchising aims to bypass these weaknesses by finding models that work, making sure that they are self-financing, and then quickly scaling them up to reach as many people as possible. It is a model that is gaining more followers and the serious interest of big and small businesses.

One example is the **Scojo Foundation** (now VisionSpring) in India, established to tackle the common problem of blurring vision as people age (presbyopia). It employs more than 560 entrepreneurs in rural villages and has sold more than 50,000 pairs of glasses since 2001.

There are critics of the BOP approach, however. Aneel Karnani from the Ross School of Business at the University of Michigan argues that from a for-profit perspective, business would be much better off targeting the needs of the growing middle classes, especially in countries such as China and India. He does acknowledge, however, that social franchising businesses such as Scojo, where social responsibility is key, are relevant to meeting the needs of the poor. – (August 2007)

- **Next Billion:** A detailed and thorough case study of how the Scojo Foundation model works: **Website:** nextbillion.net/blog/2007/07/27/new-case-study-what-work-scojo-india-foundation
- **The Social Enterprise Alliance** has built a knowledge network and extensive range of resources (including 160 case studies) on social enterprise. **Website:** se-alliance.org/resources.cfm
- **C.K. Prahalad:** A summary of the work and ideas of C.K. Prahalad. **Website:** en.wikipedia.org/wiki/C._K._Prahalad
- **World Resources Institute:** The World Resources Institute is a global environmental think tank that goes beyond research to put ideas into action. **Website:** wri.org

Microwork Pioneer

A pioneering technology social enterprise has found a way to connect people around the world to the new digital economy, transforming their lives and providing long-term employment opportunities. It is closing the digital divide in a very practical way, teaching new skills and, most importantly, providing income to the poor and vulnerable.

The San Francisco, USA-based non-profit social enterprise **Samasource** (samasource.org) uses what it calls microwork – a virtual assembly line of small tasks broken down from a larger project so that they can be completed over the Internet – to outsource work to its network of workers around the world. The tasks in this virtual piecework range from writing to transcribing to organizing online content.

The company organizes the projects using its own online work distribution system, connecting workers around the world to the SamaHub in San Francisco. Most of the workers are women, youth and refugees. When they complete their task, it is sent back to the SamaHub in San Francisco where the staff check it and assure its quality. Once approved and completed, the project is returned to the client.

The company was founded in 2008 and draws on experts in “distributed work, economic development, and outsourcing”.

The microwork is divided into three areas: content services, data enrichment and transcription. Content services can include writing descriptions for online business listings, organizing large databases on information or creating brief descriptions of existing content to make it easier for search engines to find it. “Data enrichment” tackles the vast quantity of information on the Internet that needs to be kept up to date and reliable. It also includes “tagging”, where text or images on the Internet need to have appropriate “tags” or labels. Finally, transcription services include digitizing paper documents such as receipts or books or transcribing audio and video files for the web. – (January 2012)

- **Crowd-sourcing on Mobile Phones in the Developing World:** Watch a YouTube talk by Nathan Eagle on how this works. **Website:** youtube.com/watch?v=lvz2foChQYU
- **SMS Boot Camp:** Entrepreneurial Programming and Research on Mobiles, run by MIT in Nairobi, Kenya. **Website:** media.mit.edu/ventures/EPROM/entrepreneurship.html#entrep
- **Jana** (formerly TxtEagle): Inspired by the Sanskrit word for “people”, Jana has created the first large-scale platform to enable global organizations to engage directly with emerging-market consumers in over 85 countries via their mobile phones. Jana's proprietary technology can target and reward an unprecedented 2.1 billion consumers with free mobile airtime in exchange for completing surveys or purchasing products. **Website:** jana.com/about-us

A survey of rural women market traders in Nigeria found that 95 per cent thought mobile phones had a big impact on their business. This has included fewer trips to suppliers, a quicker way to get help when they have been robbed, and opportunities to top up incomes by selling airtime, handsets or mobile phone accessories.

Business as a Tool to Do Good

The United States' fast-paced and highly inventive technology sector is reshaping philanthropy and proving that it is possible to do good and make money at the same time. The approach taken by these philanthropists is coloured by their experiences in the cut-throat world of technology, where innovation is a necessity and where reinvention and risk are daily realities.

It may seem surprising, but they share many of these qualities with millions of the world's poor as they struggle day in and day out to survive and get ahead.

Unlike the **Fairtrade** movement – whose origins are in NGOs seeking a guaranteed fair price for goods – so-called “venture philanthropists” and “social entrepreneurs” focus more on profit and growth. They draw their inspiration from the on-line networks that have rocked the business world in the past few years and look to apply a model of constant innovation.

The past 10 years have seen non-profits increasingly adopt the language and methods of business. For “venture philanthropists” and “social entrepreneurs”, philanthropy is not just about giving away money, business itself can be a tool for doing good.

The founders of highly successful online auction house Ebay, **Jeff Skoll** and **Pierre Omidyar**, are part of a wave of new thinking from California's high-tech Silicon Valley that is shaping the way huge sums of private capital become invested in social change.

Venture philanthropists focus on supporting a small portfolio of grantees who will make the most of the investment. Giving recipients large, long-term commitments, including money for infrastructure such as staff and computers, means that they do not have to spend all their time fundraising. In addition, unlike traditional philanthropists, this new breed goes right into the recipients' offices, working with them as partners instead of waiting for annual reports, and holds the grantees to quantifiable goals.

The success of Nobel Prize winner **Mohammed Yunus** and his microcredit bank, **Grameen**, has spawned an even more ambitious venture. **The Omidyar Network** – led by billionaire Omidyar – calculated that it would take between US \$50 billion and US \$60 billion to provide micro-lending services to the entire world's poor. The Network is currently putting together the financing to launch this new micro-lending facility across the world. According to Omidyar, private capital is functionally limitless. Look at it that way, he said recently to the *Los Angeles Times*, and “\$60 billion is nothing”.

Billing itself as a non-profit venture capital firm, the **Acumen Fund** uses the principles of design to solve the problems of the poor. Just as the Procter & Gambles

Acumen Fund uses entrepreneurial approaches to fight poverty.

and Motorolas of the corporate world conduct extensive ethnographic research on consumers, Acumen finances companies that create systems from the bottom up. “Start with the individuals”, said founder **Jacqueline Novogratz**. “Build systems from their perspective. Really pay attention, and then see if they can scale.”

“We are betting on entrepreneurs; we look for a strong management team,” said **Brian Trelstad**, Chief Investment Officer of the Acumen Fund. “We currently have US \$20 million in investments in six countries. We hope to take that to US \$100 million in the next five years. We are beginning to see a really rich pipeline developing in our investment countries and more high-quality investment

opportunities coming our way. We are looking for people who are passionate about their approach and who continue to build their business from the perspective of the people in need.”

Larry Page and **Sergey Brin**, the founders of the successful search engine Google, started their philanthropic wing, **Google.org**, following Ebay's example. They endowed **Google.org** with stock now worth about US \$1 billion. Then they followed Omidyar's example and set themselves up as a for-profit network.

Just as computer software and hardware manufacturers follow a constant improvement and innovation cycle, so can social entrepreneurs. – (March 2007)

Accessing Global Markets via Design Solutions

The power of design to improve products and the way in which they are manufactured is increasingly being recognized as a key component of successful economic development. A well-designed product stands a better chance in the marketplace, especially when someone is seeking out new markets in other countries.

The importance of trade – both South-South and South-North – as a reducer of poverty in developing countries is now widely acknowledged. Countries that have made the biggest gains in reducing poverty, such as Brazil, China and India, have done it through trade.

The power of trade in high-quality goods to raise incomes has been proven for more than a decade. South-South trade grew by an average of 13 per cent per year between 1995 and 2007. By 2007, South-South trade made up 20 per cent of world trade, and over a third of South-South commerce is in high-skill manufacturing. Making finished goods rather than just selling raw materials improves workers' skill levels and increases the return on trade.

Trying to get other people to desire and buy your products is very tricky, however, this is where design comes in. Good design flows from understanding the unique demands of countries and markets and what people find appealing or repellent. A product that has a successful design (people want to buy it) and is produced efficiently (a well-designed manufacturing process) will generate a good profit.

In India, the **Craft Resource Center** or **CRC Exports Limited** of Kolkata has been successfully selling leather travel bags to the Vodafone mobile phone company in the Netherlands. It did this by teaming up with **Dutch Design in Development**, an NGO focused on matching European importers and retailers and professional designers with small and medium-sized enterprises in the South.

Founded in 1989, CRC applies the concept of adding value to turn small-scale and poor artisans into successful and sustainable businesses. Many of these traditional handicraft artisans subsist on low incomes. CRC provides artisans across India with marketing, design, finance and ex-

porting help. It also connects them with other artisans and helps to divide projects among them. It uses networks to help in bad times while also sharing opportunities when they arise.

Stella van Himbergen, a project manager at DDiD, said that the concept is about introducing a new way of looking at things through the prism of design.

“Small producers in developing countries are not lacking craftsmanship”, said Himbergen, but, she added, “it is important for producers to receive support in production-led design and not only in aesthetic design.” – (May 2008)

•Dutch Design in Development: DDiD is the agency for fair design, sustainable production and fair trade. **Website:** ddid.nl/english

Women Mastering Trade Rules

Trading and selling in the marketplace can be one of the best options for poor women. By trading, women gain economic independence, learn vital business skills and enjoy the social benefits of interacting with others. However, the highly individualistic nature of market trading has its downside: traders must do everything themselves and a day not spent at market is a day's income lost.

Making market trading more efficient has huge advantages, the primary one being more money for the trader.

A typical market is a vibrant place where live animals, herbs and spices, fresh fruits and vegetables, and life's necessities compete for customers' money. The formal and informal food sector plays a crucial role in empowering women and providing food to the poor. Women are often those mostly responsible for selling fresh products and street food and running small catering operations. By being a vendor and obtaining food at a lower cost, they are able to contribute to their families' food security.

Women market traders in Nigeria are improving their efficiency and income with mobile phones. Rural women market traders in the Obiaruku market are using mobile phones to call their suppliers, access information such as commodity prices, and contact customers. A survey of the traders found that 95 per cent thought that mobile phones had a big impact on their business. This has included fewer trips to suppliers, a quicker way to get help when they have been robbed, and opportunities to top up incomes by selling airtime, handsets or mobile phone accessories. – (May 2008)

WORLD TRADE

China World's leading merchandise exporter in 2010

14.5%

World trade increase in 2010

4.7%

Average GDP growth in Africa, 2005 to 2010

US \$86 billion

Africa's commercial services exports in 2010

8%

Increase in world exports of commercial services in 2010

Source: World Trade Report 2011

African Trade Hub in China

Trade between China and Africa has surged over the past decade since China joined the WTO in 2001, from around US \$10 billion in 2000 to US \$73.3 billion in 2007, registering a year-on-year increase of 32.2 per cent. In 2008, it soared by 44.1 per cent to reach a record high of US \$106.84 billion, registering a year-on-year increase of 45.1 per cent, according to **Zhang Yongpeng** of the **Institute for West Asian and African Studies (IWAAS)**.

In the southern Chinese city of Guangzhou, a trading hub nicknamed "Africa Town" has emerged since 1998. A conglomeration of buildings around the Xiaobei road in the Yuexiu District of the city, it has been equated to the famous Chungking Mansions of Hong Kong. There are officially 20,000 African traders and entrepreneurs in the city of 18 million, but unofficial estimates put the number at more than 100,000. This African trading hub has emerged to the benefit of both Chinese and Africans. It is a coming together of small traders matching Africa's strong demand for consumer goods with China's manufacturing powerhouse.

The traders export generators, toys, mopeds, construction equipment and other products back to Africa. They act as go-betweens, bringing their local knowledge of African market demands to the Chinese manufacturers.

Citizens from over 19 African countries are represented, the majority from Nigeria.

"Almost 90 per cent of goods in African markets come from China, Thailand and Indonesia", **Sultane Barry**, president of Guangzhou's Guinean community, told *The Globe and Mail* newspaper.

Barry has an entire floor for business in a 35-storey building packed with shops, offices, freight-forwarding companies, African restaurants, hairdressers and furnished apartments for rent by the week.

Rainforest Rubbers Save Lives

Two development goals are being achieved with one innovative business in Brazil. By using natural rubber tapped from trees in the Amazon rainforest to make condoms, the vast Latin American country is able to afford the cost of distributing condoms to tackle its HIV/AIDS crisis.

Brazil currently imports more than 120 million condoms every year from China, the Republic of Korea and Thailand, making it the world's biggest single buyer of condoms. The Government gives them away for free as part of a national campaign to combat HIV. More than 620,000 people in Brazil are living with HIV out of a population of more than 186 million (UNAIDS, 2005).

The **Natex** company, co-owned by the Ministry of Public Health and the north-western state government of Acre, has established a factory to turn rubber from the world's biggest rainforest into condoms. The business has created 500 jobs at the factory and 150 jobs for the local indigenous population – the Xapuri – who are traditional rubber tappers.

The factory hopes to produce 100 million condoms a year from local rubber – just 20 million shy of all the condoms that the country currently has to import – and could even reach 270 million at full capacity.

"This product will allow people to make love with security and to better plan their futures", said **Raimundo Barros**, vice president of the local agricultural association.

"Because of this, I've managed to buy a few cows and give my family a better life", rubber tapper **Hugo Paz de Souza**, 43, told local newspaper *Página 20*. Paz de Souza said that the factory will double his income to US \$394 a month. – (May 2008)

“We’re not here for fun”, said **Ibrahim Kader Traore**, an entrepreneur from Côte d’Ivoire. “We work hard and do well. In Abidjan, people still swear by France, where you might be able to save US \$13,000 over 25 years; in China, you can have US \$130,000 in just five years.”

A trading success story, the hub ran into problems over visas in the run-up to the November 2011 Asian Games in Guangzhou, which brought increasing identity checks.

“I sell more than 50 per cent of the output of my brother-in-law’s TV factory to Africans”, one saleswoman told *The Globe and Mail*. “We need them and I’m worried there are going to be fewer of them.”

Brought together by trade and mutual interest, both communities still have much to learn about each other. Relations have had their ups and downs and Africans can face discrimination.

However, the trading relationship is teaching both sides important lessons. “The arrival of the Africans taught the Chinese how to look for business opportunities,” said Barry. “The secretaries we had here didn’t speak a word of English. Our presence started a craze for learning languages: English and French.

“The Chinese people will soon realize that it’s better for business to deal directly with ordinary Africans.”
– (December 2010)

Many large companies, such as Nestlé, target Africa’s growing consumer market.

Africa’s Consumer Market

A frenzy of activity has been building around Africa’s market opportunities and its growing middle-class consumer population. Years of steady growth rates up to 2008 and the vast, untapped opportunities on the continent have sparked interest from investors and businesses alike.

Foreign direct investment (FDI) to developing economies rose by 10 per cent in 2010 owing to fast economic recovery and increasing South-South flows. FDI inflows to Africa peaked in 2008 because of the resource boom and fell by 14 per cent to US \$50 billion in 2010 (UNCTAD). Rising FDI from Asia and Latin America has yet to match the decline from developed countries – still the source of the majority of FDI to Africa.

However, foreign direct investment to Africa had risen sixfold to US \$58.56 billion between 2000 and 2009 (UNCTAD). The amount going to manufacturing and services has been growing despite the slow down in 2009 because of the global economic downturn. Africa’s 11 largest economies are now being seen as the next to match Brazil and the Russian Federation, economic stars of the last few years.

The continent as a whole forms the 10th

largest economy in the world. Of Africa’s more than 1 billion people, 900 million can be classified as part of the consumer economy. Out of this group, there is a third – approximately 300 million people – who make modest sums by Western standards, about US \$200 a month, but have spare cash to buy things such as mobile phones, DVDs and new clothes or pay for better schools. They are the population that is overlooked when attention is focused only on the very poor living on less than US \$2 a day.

This vast group is captured in the book, **Africa Rising**, by University of Texas professor **Vijay Mahajan**, which details the phenomenon of Africa’s middle-class consumer society. He calls this group of middle-class consumers “Africa 2”, with the desperately poor called “Africa 3s”, and the extremely rich, “Africa 1s.”

“By 2040, the continent will be home to one in five of the planet’s young people and will have the world’s largest working-age population”, according to Charles Roxburgh and Susan Lund, authors of a study for the McKinsey Global Institute.

“If Africa can give its young people sufficient education and skills, they could be a substantial source of consumption and production in years ahead.” – (January 2011)

Indonesia Best for Entrepreneurs

A global survey has unearthed hotspots across the global South for start-up businesses and private enterprise. It shows that there are now many places in the South where people are actively encouraged to start businesses and engage in innovation and enterprise. The top place in the world for entrepreneurship, according to the survey for the British Broadcasting Corporation (BBC), is Indonesia.

The poll shows that Indonesians perceive their country as a place where it is easy to put ideas into practice. Innovation and creativity are highly valued in Indonesia as well, two important elements of business success. Asia as a whole, with a few exceptions, stood out for valuing these qualities.

India came second in the survey, while China and Nigeria were also perceived by their own people as relatively favourable places for new businesses.

The survey for the BBC's **Extreme World** TV series polled more than 24,000 people in 24 countries. Respondents were asked whether innovation was highly valued in their country; whether it was hard for people like them to start a business; whether entrepreneurs were highly valued; and whether people with good ideas could usually put them into practice.

Interestingly, not only were several countries in East Asia and the Pacific doing well, but three sub-Saharan African countries - Ghana, Kenya and Nigeria - also ranked above the global average.

The survey found that work still needed to be done in Latin America. While Mexico and Peru scored highly, Brazil and Colombia ranked below average.

So, what are the things that make Indonesia so positive for entrepreneurs and private business? And what do they do - or not do - for small business start-ups?

According to **Bali International Consulting Group**, the Indonesian economy is highly dependent on small and medium-sized enterprises: they make up 99.95 per cent of the total number of enterprises and provide most of the country's jobs. Authorities have identified a problem with the sector, however: productivity per worker is very low compared to that of large enterprises. Poor productivity matters because it means that people are working very hard for a low return and this affects the overall standard of living in the country and its human development.

The Government of Indonesia has set about boosting productivity in the sector, adopting a 'clustering' approach in partnership with non-governmental organizations (NGOs). Like-minded businesses tend to cluster together across the archipelago of islands that makes up the country. By targeting these places with resources and support, the Government can use those resources more efficiently. The country has a dedicated ministry for small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) and a wide range of businesses and services targeting them. From dedicated trading and office facilities to an online marketplace to display, trade and sell SME products, extensive resources are applied to give SMEs a boost.

Best Countries for Entrepreneurs

Top Five:

- Indonesia
- USA
- Canada
- India
- Australia

Bottom Five:

- Russian Federation
- Italy
- Turkey
- Egypt
- Colombia

Source: BBC/Globescan

From past experience, Indonesia learned that it was more effective to use business development services in clusters to promote and develop SMEs rather than centralized, top-down government models or other approaches.

As Bali International Consulting Group notes, "The government has introduced many models for promoting SMEs, including business incubators, business consulting clinics and technology centers. However, those sponsoring programmes have not been productive and could not sustain themselves for a long time. The government then turned to supporting BDS (Business Development Services) providers to serve a certain cluster in a selected area."

Developed countries such as the United States grew their wealth significantly by allowing entrepreneurs and small and medium-sized enterprises to flourish. The USA's highly innovative and globe-straddling high-tech and information technology businesses would not have been so successful without entrepreneurs. Think of Bill Gates, one of the founders of Microsoft, or Steve Jobs, one of the pioneers behind the Apple computer brand. - (June 2011)

Model City to Test the New Urbanism Concept in India

India's phenomenal economic growth rate – averaging over 7 per cent per year over the past decade – has been the force behind an expanding middle-class population, now estimated at 50 million (McKinsey). Forecasts see the middle class swelling from 5 per cent of the Indian population to 40 per cent by 2025.

With 30 per cent of the population living in urban areas and cities contributing 60 per cent of the country's GDP and 90 per cent of government revenues (*Wall Street Journal*), city-dwellers' fate is critical to the functioning of the economy.

This is where the new city concept of **Lavasa** (lavasa.com) comes in. This new community sits nestled in picturesque mountains and features promenades, sidewalk cafes and ice cream parlours but none of the clichéd fixtures of today's Indian cities: rickshaws, noise and pollution, poor sanitation and overcrowding. It has apartment houses in mustard, terra cotta, ochre, olive and beige.

Lavasa is also going to have a medical campus, luxury hotels, boarding schools, sports academies, a golf course, a space camp, animation and film studios, software-development companies, biotech labs and law and architectural companies – a thoroughly “knowledge economy” mix that India's aspiring classes wish to see the country embrace for its future development. The people behind Lavasa see it as a new model of governance and urban development for India in the 21st century.

Lavasa is located in Western Ghats, 200 kilometres southeast of Mumbai, India's financial and entertainment capital, and 65 kilometres west of Pune, a center for software programming and computer animation.

Lavasa's colourful and detailed website boasts of it as a “private hill city being developed by Lavasa Corporation Limited where people can live, work, learn and play in harmony with nature”. It is billed as “an inclusive city, based on the principles of New Urbanism”.

The master plan is to house more than 300,000 people in five linked towns.

The first town, Dasve, will be completed in 2011. Its houses are almost sold out, according to its developers.

Lavasa is the concept of **Ajit Gulabchand**, chairman of Hindustan Construction Company, an Indian company with extensive experience building bridges and dams.

The development is located in the remote hills along the Varasgaon Lake, a reservoir providing water to Pune. Lavasa Hill City covers “25,000 acres with 60 kms of lake-front” according to its website. The land had originally been designated for holiday homes, but this seemed too small an aspiration.

Lavasa will be governed by a private corporation. It is also being planned according to the principles of new urbanism (newurbanism.org) – a belief in cities built around walkability, not cars, where business and residential sit side-by-side, with mixed-income housing and a great deal of green space for parks.

This thoroughly modern approach has startled prospective buyers of homes, puzzled there were no water tanks on the roofs or septic tanks for each house, something they had come to expect in current Indian cities.

The Lavasa Corporation has hired an American city administrator, **Scot Wrighton**, to run the new city.

He told *The Atlantic* magazine that Lavasa offered him “a chance to build a new governance model for a country where governance at the municipal level does not work”. – (September 2011)

•**Urbanized:** New documentary *Urbanized* gives a passionate overview of the challenges facing the rapidly urbanizing world around us.

Website: urbanizedfilm.com

•**Global Urbanist:** Excellent expert-contributed website created by alumni from the London School of Economics and Political Science (LSE). **Website:** globalurbanist.com

Mongolia: Healthy Urban Lifestyles

In the Northeast Asian country of Mongolia, landlocked between China and the Russian Federation, the traditional diet is based on the nomadic ways of its herders. Rich in meat and milk products, it is a diet that has evolved from the need to survive in a harsh climate doing hard physical labour – winter temperatures can drop below minus 50 degrees Celsius.

Social changes brought about by Mongolia's economic journey since embracing free markets and democracy in the early 1990s have led to a growing urban population.

According to the World Diabetes Foundation, 10 per cent of Mongolia's population is at risk of the disease, which it calls a lurking catastrophe.

In response to these problems, increasing awareness of healthy lifestyles has led to some new business ventures in the capital, Ulaanbaatar. The opening of an organic vegetarian restaurant and shop in 2010, the Organic Café Shop, was reported by Green Traveller Guides.

Started by business partner sisters **Bayarmaa Jarantai** and **Enkhmaa Jarantai** with nephew Lkhagvasuren, the modest four-table restaurant and shop are a mini revolution for a country as meat-loving as Mongolia. It serves up organic vegetarian meals and sells certified organic products. The spark of inspiration came when Bayarmaa read three books on the macrobiotic diet translated into Mongolian. The macrobiotic diet avoids highly processed foods and uses grains, beans and vegetables as its staples. – (November 2010)

Shoes with Sole: Ethiopian Web Success Story

Ethiopia's bustling capital, Addis Ababa, is experiencing a building and business boom. Foreign investors and Ethiopia's entrepreneurial global diaspora are investing again in the country, but Ethiopia still relies for most of its foreign currency wealth on exports of unprocessed coffee beans and leather hides — a model that leaves the bulk of the profits made outside of Ethiopia.

One shoe company, however, provides an example of a home-grown business that is finding success in the international marketplace while repatriating most of the profits for its goods back to Ethiopia, creating jobs and local wealth.

Ethiopia's economy is mostly dependent on agriculture, which accounts for 60 per cent of exports and 80 per cent of employment (CIA World Factbook). The country has a tiny private sector and a high rate of youth unemployment. It is difficult to find funding for small businesses, yet because of the high population growth, the country needs to create more jobs.

The Economist magazine has forecast that Ethiopia's economy will grow by 7 per cent in 2010, becoming the fifth-fastest-growing economy in the world and on course to surpass Kenya to become East Africa's biggest economy. While this sounds impressive, the country has to run hard to create enough jobs to meet the needs of its growing population and still faces significant food security problems.

One company, **soleRebels**, is combining a clever twist on a local tradition – recycling rubber from old truck tires into shoes, locally known as selate shoes – with sophisticated design concepts and high-quality craftsmanship to make a global footwear hit.

Co-founder and managing director **Bethlehem Tilahun Alemu**, a 30-year-old African web-vending entrepreneur, has turned this local craft into a global fashion hit by adding colourful cotton and leather uppers to the tire shoes. The recycled rubber shoes come in many styles: from handmade flip-flops to boat shoes, loafers and athletic trainers resembling the popular Converse sports shoe from the United States (converse.com).

SoleRebels' shoe factory is on the outskirts of Addis Ababa in the historic village of Zenabework. Despite its location, it is reaching the international markets through online retailers such as Amazon.com.

The secret to this small start-up's success? Apart from great shoes and funky design, Alemu puts it down to attitude: "We are sitting in Addis Ababa but acting like an

Shoe entrepreneur, Bethlehem Tilahun Alemu.

American company", she told *The Guardian* newspaper.

It doesn't hurt that Alemu is also money-smart: she is a former accountant.

Started five years ago, soleRebels now employs 45 full-time staff making 500 pairs of shoes a day. The shoes cost between US \$33 and US \$64. They are also being sold in Japan and the United Kingdom on Amazon's shoe-selling website, javari.co.uk.

In 2010, Alemu hopes that soleRebels will make US \$481,000 but soleRebels has an even more ambitious goal: to become "the Timberland or Sketchers of Africa".

Timberland (timberland.com/home/index.jsp), an American shoe and boot maker, has been a pioneer in high-quality leather footwear, breaking new ground in adopting green manufacturing processes and exploiting the power of the web by allowing customers to customize their footwear.

SoleRebels has cleverly exploited the advantages of the

global marketplace to grow its customers and profits.

The business has done this with just one leg-up: a line of credit from the Government to help with large orders.

With 6.2 million people out of a population of 80 million needing food aid, Ethiopia is still highly dependent on international aid, but Alemu is showing that there is a way to build a sustainable successful business.

Inspiration for Alemu came when she was thinking about what Ethiopian product could be produced in a sustainable way. She remembered the sandals worn in the country.

"Recycling is a way of life here – you don't throw things away that you can use again and again", she said. "I wanted to build on that idea."

Ethiopian shoemakers have had a difficult time in recent years, trying to compete with less expensive Chinese imports. Rather than just trying to come up with a shoe that was even less costly than the Chinese ones, however,

soleRebels decided to build a business selling shoes to the more lucrative export market.

Alemu reasoned that good design would attract a higher price. She did research on the Internet to find out which designs worked well and what were the latest footwear trends.

This research formed the basis of her range of shoes, which have catchy names like Class Act or Gruuv Thong. The sandals and flip-flops are either cotton covered or leather covered. The Urban Runner shoe sells best and is inspired by the Converse All Star sneaker.

SoleRebels has a regular supplier of old truck tires and inner tubes and has women weave and dye the cotton, jute and hemp uppers for the shoes. Almost all materials are locally sourced. Old army uniforms are cannibalized for their camouflage pattern.

SoleRebels has also been canny in seeking **Fair Trade** certification (fairtrade.org.uk) to help with marketing and selling the shoes.

To increase the market for the shoes, Alemu bombarded American retailers with emails and shoe samples to pique their interest. Because of the U.S. **African Growth and Opportunity Act** (agoa.gov), soleRebels' shoes can be imported into the United States duty-free: a big price advantage in

the U.S. marketplace that has helped to grab the interest of retailers such as Whole Foods and Urban Outfitters.

This interest soon snowballed, and people were placing orders through the soleRebels website. Orders come by courier from Ethiopia in about a week to the United States.

With all this interest building, Amazon, the leviathan online retailer, decided to become a customer for the shoes. Online retailing has been a huge boost to the growth of soleRebels. According to Alemu, it has enabled the company "to understand the market needs and demands in real time" – a huge advantage to a start-up company far away from its markets.

There is another advantage to using the web to grow a business: it has enabled soleRebels to take greater control of the whole process. The company negotiates directly with retailers, handling orders and credit collection, and this ensures that most of the profits of the business return to Ethiopia.

Making soleRebels quickly profitable has been a benefit to its workers. Starters at the company make US \$1.92 a day while experienced shoe makers earn US \$11 a day (a good wage in Ethiopia).

"In Ethiopia we have become used to taking money from the West, to always getting help", Alemu told *The Guardian*. "That does not make for a sustainable economy. We need to solve our own problems."

Also, success brings the opportunity for further growth. SoleRebels is now building a solar-powered factory to replace its current workshop.

In addition, there is a steely pride in the firm's success: "People buy soleRebels because they are good, not just because they are green or from Ethiopia", Alemu said. "Our product speaks for itself." – (January 2010)

- The online service **CafePress** is a specially designed one-stop shop that lets entrepreneurs upload their designs and then sell them via their online payment and worldwide shipping service.
Website: cafepress.com/cp/info/sell
- iFashion:** This web portal run from South Africa has all the latest business news on fashion in Africa and profiles of up-and-coming designers.
Website: ifashion.co.za/index.php?option=com_frontpage&Itemid=1

Solar Sisters Doing It for Themselves: Tackling African Light Famine

A social enterprise is seeking to capture the power of the sun to bring light and economic opportunity to women in Africa. Using a direct-marketing distribution system, it sells solar lamps and lanterns to some of Africa’s remotest communities. Solar Sister, launched in Uganda in 2010, is hoping to do for power generation what mobile phones have done for communication in Africa: make a technological leap to a model of grass roots power generation rather than waiting for large-scale power schemes to eventually reach the poor and rural people.

More than 1.7 billion people around the world have no domestic electricity supply, of whom more than 500 million live in sub-Saharan Africa (World Bank).

Solar power is being creatively used in many countries to tackle energy poverty and give women, in particular, viable sources of income. In India, whole villages are already using solar energy to improve their standard of living. Various companies and projects are selling inexpensive solar appliances – from cooking stoves to lanterns and power generators – across the country.

A report by the International Finance Corporation called the sub-Saharan solar market the largest in the world: 65 million would-be customers, who could access off-grid lighting over the next five years (IFC). The report anticipated high growth rates of 40 to 50 per cent for anyone entering the market, with less than 1 per cent of the market currently being served.

Being able to see at night unleashes a vast range of possibilities, such as being able to work or study later. For the very poor, however, lighting is often the biggest household expense.

As **Solar Sister** founder **Katherine Lucey** points out, many households “rely on kerosene lanterns and candles for light. They spend up to 40 per cent of their family income on energy that is inefficient, insufficient and hazardous. Widespread use of kerosene has an adverse impact on local air quality as well as on global climate change.

“Poor lighting, smoke and rudimentary lanterns are responsible for a large number of infections and burn injuries. Within the household, women are responsible for kerosene purchases and use – in order for

“ In order for new clean energy technology to be adopted at the household level, women have to “buy in” to the technology ”

new clean energy technology to be adopted at the household level, women have to “buy in” to the technology.”

The challenge is to find an affordable – and sustainable – way to bring electricity and energy to people living in remote and rural areas. These are people who face stark options: remain off-grid and energy poor, or abandon their communities and join the many millions across the global South on the march to urban and semi-urban areas in search of income and opportunity.

Lucey says that mass urban migration could be “a recipe for disaster”.

“In a country like Uganda, with a population of 32 million people, it is not possible to have them all move to Kampala to access electricity”, she said. “It would overburden already stretched infrastructure and services and disrupt the social and economic structures of an entire population. In the end, it can challenge the stability of entire nations.”

The Solar Sister direct-marketing model works like this: micro-investment capital of US \$500 is invested in one Solar Sister Entrepreneur and she receives a “business in a bag”: a start-up kit of inventory, training and marketing resources. As her own boss, she has a strong incentive to succeed. She uses the money to purchase a consignment of lamps or lanterns, which she then sells, encouraging people to replace kerosene lamps with solar lamps, which are healthier, safer and better for the environment. She is encouraged to use her existing networks of family, friends and neighbours to reach rural and hard-to-reach customers.

After selling the first consignment of lamps, the Solar Sister receives training in marketing and inventory and business skills. She can then move on to be a team leader and recruit other Solar Sisters. She earns a commission from the lamp sales, which help to improve her ability to pay for healthcare, education and food for her family. She then repays the cash for the lamps and the cycle starts all over again with a new consignment.

The model will sound familiar to many: it has built successful marketing machines such as the famous all-women’s make-up and beauty products seller, Avon, or the other famous direct marketing behemoth, Amway.

The Solar Sister model relies heavily on the success of word of mouth to grow.

“What we have found is that the women are the best distribution system for bringing new technology to rural households since they sell through their trusted networks of family, friends and neighbours”, Lucey said. “They use the lamps themselves, and then talk passionately about the benefits: the better light, the money they save by not having to buy kerosene, the amount of time their children are able to study, the cleaner air and safer environment for their kids.”

According to Lucey, the business model “brings solar technology right to the women’s doorstep. The Solar Sister business model developed as a grass-roots solution to the gender-based technology gap. Women make up 70 per cent of the rural poor but are often left out ‘in the dark’ when it comes to technology solutions.”

It is still early days for Solar Sister, which has been in operation for just over a year and now has 107 Solar Sister Entrepreneurs working in 10 teams reaching 34 communities in three countries: Uganda, Rwanda and Sudan. Lucey says that the goal is to build a network of 1,500 female entrepreneurs in Africa over the next two years, benefiting more than 1 million people.

Apart from the business model and the new technology, there is a radical concept at the heart of Solar Sister: to replicate for electricity the phenomenal growth of mobile telephony across the continent. In just five years, the availability

of mobile phones in Africa increased by 550 per cent.

“Distributed energy, such as solar, puts the investment in energy generation rather than transmission and breaks the problem into smaller, achievable components that do not have to wait for political processes for implementation”, explains Lucey. “It allows for the possibility that people can solve their own problems rather than wait for government or NGOs to solve their energy problems for them. Distributed solar has the potential to leap-frog the 20th century grid-based solution, much like mobile phones have done in the telecom industry.”

– (April 2011)

•**D.light Design:** Their lights use LEDs (light-emitting diodes) (en.wikipedia.org/wiki/LED_lamp) and are four times brighter than a kerosene lantern according to D.Light Design. **Website:** dlightdesign.com

•**Lighting Africa:** Lighting Africa, a joint IFC and World Bank programme, is helping to develop commercial off-grid lighting markets in sub-Saharan Africa as part of the World Bank Group’s wider efforts to improve access to energy. Lighting Africa is mobilizing the private sector to build sustainable markets to provide safe, affordable and modern off-grid lighting to 2.5 million people in Africa by 2012 and to 250 million people by 2030. **Website:** lightingafrica.org

•**How We Made It Africa:** A website detailing success stories on businesses investing in Africa and how people are making the most of opportunities on the continent. **Website:** howwemadeitinafrica.com

•**Solar Lighting for the Base of the Pyramid – Overview of an Emerging Market,** a report by the International Finance Corporation finding that Africa will be the world’s largest market for solar portable lights by 2015. The report addresses market trends and statistics at a global level with more detailed analysis for the African market. **Website:** lightingafrica.org/market-intelligence/market-trends-assessment.html

•**Solar Power Answers** is a one-stop-shop for everything to do with solar power. It has a design manual and guides to the complex world of solar power equipment. **Website:** solar-power-answers.co.uk/index.php

South African Wine Industry Uncorks Opportunities

Wine-making is one of South Africa's oldest industries and plays a key part in the country's economy, and now both wine-making and wine production are being transformed, creating new economic opportunities. Once seen only as the preserve of the country's white minority, wine is slowly becoming a black thing, too.

With exports growing from less than 50 million litres in 1994 to more than 400 million litres in 2008 – year-on-year growth of 17 per cent – it is an industry that would be remiss if it did not share the profits of this success with the 80 per cent of South Africans who are black.

Since the end of the racist Apartheid regime in the mid-1990s, various government and industry initiatives have begun to diversify the country's wine-making industry and, in turn, introduce more black South Africans to the pleasures of drinking this fine local product.

One product of this shift in sentiment is Zimbabwean **Tariro Masayiti**. A vintner for the prestigious South African winery **Nederburg**, he made history by being commissioned to create two of the three official wines selected for the 2010 football World Cup in South Africa. His Sauvignon Blanc and Dry Rosé were drunk while fans watched the competition.

He says that his introduction to the world of wine-making came about by chance.

"My brother used to work at a farm close to the Mukuyu wineries in Marondera (Zimbabwe)", he said. "During my days at the university, he recommended I do general work at the winery as I needed pocket money and something to help my family with.

"It was here that I got interested in wine-making. I used to see visitors from all over the world and some of them encouraged me to take up wine-making as a career. I applied and was accepted for a place at the University

of Stellenbosch where I studied viticulture and oenology (winery)", Masayiti told SW Radio Africa news.

"I was headhunted by Nederburg before I even finished my studies."

Masayiti's job involves testing the grapes that go into the winery's product. "I smell them and at the same time look for specific characters and flavours", he said.

Another symbol of these changes is **Vernon Henn**, general manager of **Thandi** wines. He worked his way up to this prestigious role in the white-dominated South African wine industry from being an office cleaner. Thandi is the first wine brand in the world entirely owned and run by a black collective.

Thandi (which means "nurturing love" in the Xhosa language) was started in 1995 and became the world's first Fair Trade-certified wine in 2003. It sells cabernet sauvignon, merlot, pinot noir and other wine varietals.

"The whole of the industry has been changing slowly", Henn told *The Guardian* newspaper. "We can now up the pace of transformation. There's still a misconception that anything from black-owned manufacturing has to be inferior. We have always focused on quality and tried to redress misconceptions about black-owned labels."

Other black-owned labels include **M'huDi**, **Ses'fikile**, led by three former township schoolteachers; and **Seven Sisters**, cultivated by seven sisters.

"We are a tiny minority but we are here to stay", said **Vivian Kleynhans** of the **African Vintners Alliance**, comprising eight companies led by black women. "So they will just have to accept us."

Another success is the **Indaba** brand first launched in the US in 1996, shortly after South Africa became a democratic republic. "Indaba" is the Zulu word for "a meeting of the minds", or "a traditional gathering of tribal leaders for sharing ideas".

The brand was created as a celebration of the democratization process in South Africa, and from its inception, the wines have conveyed the spirit of South Africa to the world's wine drinkers.

The Indaba range of wines consists of the Indaba Sauvignon Blanc, Indaba Chenin Blanc, Indaba Chardonnay, Indaba Merlot and Indaba Shiraz.

There is also the **Soweto Wine Festival** held in the Soweto township near Johannesburg. Soweto was a center of the resistance against the Apartheid regime and still has a very poor slum area in its midst, but it is also home to the new and rising black middle class. Many parts of Soweto could now pass for affluent suburbs in any wealthy country. Hatched as an idea in 2004, the wine festival is about "introducing South Africa's quality wines to the remaining 80 per cent of our population", says **Mnikelo Mangciphu**, co-founder of the Soweto Wine Festival. "Wine is not only for white South Africans to enjoy. It should be a way of life for all South Africans."

Mangciphu is also the owner and manager of the only wine shop in Soweto, Morara Wine & Spirit Emporium, which he launched after the first Soweto Wine Festival in 2005.

The idea behind the festival is to shift attitudes in South Africa about wine drinking. Soweto has been the home to many trends in the country, from politics to fashion to pop music, so it seemed the right place to start shifting attitudes towards wine. The number of participants has grown from 3,000 people to 5,520. Five years after it began, the festival showcases wines from 103 wineries.

Mangciphu had spotted a shift in drinking habits away from just beer so he opened his wine boutique in Soweto to cater to these new tastes. The shop is an elegant place, with wooden shelves displaying the bottles of wine.

South Africa's wine industry now employs around 257,000 people directly and indirectly, including farm labourers and those involved in packaging, retailing and wine tourism.

Wine tourism alone employs over 59,000 people. The Western Cape region, home to much of the wine industry, has seen its economy grow on the back of wine tourism.
– (October 2010)

South Africa's wine industry in 2010 was supporting about 275,600 workers, with the work divided between 58 per cent unskilled, 29 per cent semi-skilled and 13 per cent skilled (SAWIS).

- **Soweto Wine Festival:** The Soweto Wine Festival introduces South Africa's quality wines to the remaining 80 per cent of the population. **Website:** sowetowine-festival.co.za/About.htm
- **African American Wine Tasting Society:** The AAWTS' focus is on exposing individuals to an array of wines in a comfortable, relaxed and unpretentious setting. **Website:** aawts.org
- **Indaba wines available online:** **Website:** snooth.com/wines/indaba
- **Blackpreneur blog:** **Website:** blackpreneur.net/blog
- Watch video interview recorded in the **Morara Wines** shop in Soweto. **Website:** mg.co.za/multimedia/2010-09-02-wine-takes-off-in-soweto/low

Putting Quality and Design at the Centre of Chinese Fashion

Fashion is big business, and increasingly consumers care about where a garment comes from as well as how it looks.

The past decade has seen growing awareness of the sourcing of materials for fashion.

Concerns about how the global fashion industry functions and its impact on the environment have given rise to savvy retailers who take care over the sourcing of their materials and the working conditions of their employees. Consumers have shown a willingness to pay a little more to know that a garment is sustainably produced and has the lowest possible impact on the environment.

The global textile industry is the second-biggest consumer of water in the world. The dyeing processes used by manufacturers do extensive damage to the water table that is used for drinking water.

In China, there have been violent demonstrations over working conditions and increasing concern over the health consequences of many modern manufacturing methods. For a real

change to occur, new business models need to emerge, and consumers and customers need to be educated to demand better-quality, low- or non-polluting products.

One business has accomplished something remarkable: it has succeeded in producing high-quality, ethically sourced products while also employing vulnerable people who have significant care duties and need a flexible and understanding employer.

NuoMi (nuomishanghai.com) has three stores and a store/design studio in Shanghai, China. The company's name means "sticky rice" in Mandarin. It was founded by Filipino fashion designer **Bonita Lim**, a mother of four, who uses her business to help single mothers and the less fortunate.

NuoMi is also pioneering sustainable and green goods for the Chinese market. This is unusual in a country known more for its sweatshop, low-wage manufacturing industries that have helped to make China an economic powerhouse. – (October 2011)

- **Ecodesignfair:** Eco Design Fair is a bi-annual grass-roots community event whose purpose is to showcase eco-conscious designers and products to general consumers. **Website:** ecodesignfair.cn
- **Nest:** Another eco-conscious design company in Shanghai. Its motto is "design with a conscience". **Website:** nestshanghai.com/nest.html

Mapping Beirut Brings City to Light

As cities in the global South grow ever larger, their often-chaotic evolution can create sprawling urban mazes that would confuse even the brightest brains.

When a city fails to communicate its treasures, something is lost for both parties: businesses lose valuable customers, and the visitor or resident fails to grasp what is on offer. How will you find the restaurant you want or that shop with the just-right fashions?

Beirut is a city that has had its ups and downs. Once called "the Paris of the Middle East" for its beauty and cosmopolitan atmosphere, it descended into decades of civil war and unrest from 1975. As recently as 2006, Lebanon fought a war with Israel. Beirut's residents have grown used to a city of turmoil and rapid change. They also have grown used to a city that people navigate by landmarks rather than street names.

Bahi Ghubril became fed up with the frustration of having to always ask people for directions to get around the city or getting stuck behind drivers begging pedestrians for directions.

Inspired by London's famous A-Z (a-zmaps.co.uk), he researched and launched the **Zawarib Beirut Road Atlas** in 2005 (twitter.com/#!/zawaribworld) and (facebook.com/zawarib).

It is part of a new trend across the global South: people using the slew of new information technologies and online resources to map and discover their neighbourhoods and cities. In turn, this is fuelling economic growth as people can find businesses and promote themselves to buyers and customers. – (October 2011)

- **Zawarib Beirut Road Atlas:** The Zawarib Beirut can be purchased from Amazon's website. **Website:** amazon.co.uk/Zawarib-Beirut-Greater-Atlas/dp/9953005311
- **Google Maps:** A treasure trove of global maps and data. **Website:** maps.google.co.uk
- **Google Maps for mobile:** Use Google Maps on your phone and never carry a paper map again. **Website:** google.co.uk/mobile/maps

Ghana's Funeral Economy Innovates and Exports

The West African country of Ghana's funeral economy is attracting innovation and grabbing attention outside the country. Ghana's elaborate – but expensive – funeral rituals provide craftsmen with a good income, and new products are being introduced to handle the financial consequences of this unavoidable fact of life.

As Africa undergoes the biggest shift from rural to urban in its history, the continent is experiencing a technology boom, led mainly by the mobile phone. Mobile phones have become important transactional tools in daily life, enabling people to communicate and to do business thanks to micropayments and prepay.

It is in this context that Ghana's flamboyant and vibrant funeral ceremonies have become an economy unto themselves.

Ghana's crafty craftsmen have developed a global reputation for their bizarre but highly skilled coffin designs. They build striking coffins of elaborate designs and shapes and flamboyant colours. The coffins usually take on the shape of an aspect of the deceased's former profession or vocation. For example, a pilot gets buried in a mock-up of the plane that he flew or a farmer is buried in his main crop, a giant corn cob.

It is proof that the creative economy works and adds value to existing products and services. What were just simple coffins for a utilitarian task (burying the dead) becomes an elaborate work of art and transforms a burial into a grander experience.

One of the most popular designs is the now-ubiquitous and much-coveted mobile phone, Africa's great electronic connector, and it is the mobile phone that is allowing people to buy life insurance to be able to pay for the coffins and elaborate funerals.

Mobile money is a dynamic and fast-growing industry that is firmly established in the global South. Some are forecasting that the market in mobile payments will reach US \$60 billion by 2015.

A range of companies are now offering life insurance policies that can be paid for in "micropayments" by mobile phone. This is an important service for people who may not have a formal bank account and who can be devastated by the costs of a family member's funeral.

The two companies pioneering this "micro-insurance" service are **Hollard Insurance** (hollard.co.za) and **Mobile Financial Services Africa** (mfsafrica.com). Both are offering funeral insurance by mobile phones. Working with **MTN** – Africa's largest mobile phone group (mtn.com.gh) – they are launching the mi-Life insurance product, sold for between US 0.80 cents and US \$4 for a month's coverage.

MTN pioneered its **Mobile Money** service in 2009. Out of 9 million MTN mobile phone subscribers in Ghana, 1.8 million have signed up

Wooden coffin modeled on the iconic 'Mercedes Benz' design.

for the opportunity to pay bills and make other financial transactions over their mobile phones.

Selling life insurance by mobile phones is radically altering the marketplace for this product. Life insurance had been out of the reach of most Ghanaians just as bank accounts were beyond the reach of the poor.

Jeremy Leach, head of micro-insurance at Hollard, told AllWestAfrica (allwestafrica.com) that 55 per cent of Ghanaians say they cannot afford life insurance. "In terms of affordability, we've tried to address that."

For the coffin craftsmen, the fast-growing economy of African online shopping is helping with sales. The elaborate craft coffins can be bought online from various platforms including eShopAfrica.com, which promises to sell "fair trade direct from Africa". Its dedicated Ghana coffin pages (eshopafrika.com/acatalog/Ga_Coffins.html) advertise small coffins that take a month to make, and larger ones can take up to three months to build. Prices advertised on the eShop site range from US \$1,500 for a full-sized, six-foot coffin to US \$175 for a "desk top chest".

Designs range from a mobile phone to a Ferrari race car to a computer mouse, but it is not just the resting places for the deceased that are on sale. The cabinet- and coffin-making skills are also turned to making a wide range of storage cabinets in bright colours and imaginative shapes, from a football to a red pepper and a beer-bottle-shaped drinks cabinet. – (April 2011)

•**ShopAfrica53:** Pledging in its motto to reach "every African nook and cranny", ShopAfrica53 is an online shopping portal similar to famous brands such as Amazon or eBay but focused entirely on giving African traders the ability to sell across the continent and to the world online. **Website:** shopafrika53.com

•**Going into Darkness: Fantastic Coffins from Africa** by Thierry Secretan details the culture and the craftsmen, behind the iconic coffins. **Website:** www.amazon.com/exec/obidos/ASIN/0500278393/cordelinetwebstu

Afro Coffee undertook a major re-design and adopted a new concept in order to boost its brand identity. By infusing the spirit of Africa and its design aesthetics into all aspects of the café and its products – coffee, tea, fabrics, fashion – Afro Coffee has been able to develop a seamless image that is unforgettable.

Afro Coffee's website includes a video tour of the café and introduction to the "Afro dude" character and a short cartoon video adventure.

As the brand developed, a range of teas were produced using only African teas such as Rooibos, a non-caffeine root.

Afro Coffee: Blending Good Design and Coffee

The importance of good design and a strong brand in the success of a business cannot be emphasized enough. That extra effort and thought can take a business from local success to regional and even to becoming a global player. As consultants KPMG make clear, "For many businesses, the strength of their brands is a key driver of profitability and cash flow". Yet the majority of small businesses fail to think about their brand values or how design will improve their product or service.

The case of **Afro Coffee** from Cape Town, South Africa, shows how a small and humble café can raise its ambitions and its profits. It re-vamped its modestly successful café into a brand with global ambitions. By undertaking a thorough and comprehensive brand development inspired by the colourful vibes of Africa, Afro Coffee has built a consistent image from the design of its café and shop to its wide range of branded teas, coffees and fashion wear – all sold in the café, on the web and through distribution deals with other shops.

– (July 2007)

•**Brandchannel:** The world's only online exchange about branding, packed with resources, debates and contacts to help businesses intelligently build their brand.

Website: brandchannel.com

•**Branding Strategy Insider:** Small businesses looking to develop their brand can find resources at Branding Strategy Insider.

Website: brandingstrategyinsider.com

•**Dutch Design in Development:** Dutch designers are able to offer free support to new and small businesses in developing countries looking to export products to Europe.

Website: didid.nl

Rwandan Coffee Brand Boost

A successful Rwandan company is using coffee shops to promote the nation's high-quality coffee brands at home and abroad. Started by two Rwandan entrepreneurs in 2007, **Bourbon Coffee** now has three shops in the country's capital, Kigali, and a savvily positioned shop in Washington, D.C.

While Rwandan coffee has built a good international reputation, the country's more than 500,000 coffee farmers (mostly small-scale) previously depended on the product's reputation alone.

The Bourbon Coffee chain of shops (taking its name from the high-quality Bourbon coffee varietal that accounts for the majority of Rwandan coffee) opened its first shop in Kigali in 2007. Started by **Emmanuel Murekezi** and **Arthur Karulewa**, two Rwandans living

in the United States, it is modelled on the popular American brand, Starbucks. The entrepreneurs admired the coffee culture experience found at Starbucks. Just as Starbucks heavily markets its complete quality control over the coffee experience, their philosophy is to produce great coffee from "crop to cup".

– (August 2010)

Good African Coffee

Over at **Good African Coffee**, Ugandan entrepreneur **Andrew Rugasira** is pioneering new ways to process coffee in Africa. He set up Uganda's first enterprise to make instant coffee two years ago. The company's products are cleverly designed and packaged and are sold in distinct colour-coordinated packets.

"For decades, Africans have produced what they do not consume and consumed what they do not produce", Rugasira told the *Wall Street Journal*.

– (December 2011)

Southern Innovator KNOWLEDGE SUMMARY

Issue 2 of **Southern Innovator** joins a growing stable of off- and online resources capturing unique knowledge on Southern innovation.

5 E-newsletter

Published every month since 2006, the Development Challenges, South-South Solutions e-newsletter has chronicled the many changes in the global South: from the rise of mobile phones to the move to cities and urban areas to the proliferation of innovative solutions.

Youth 1

2

The **Southern Innovator website archive** presents by theme the back catalogue of stories from the Development Challenges, South-South Solutions e-newsletter. It also joins an extensive range of resources offered on the web portal for the UNDP Special Unit for South-South Cooperation (ssc.undp.org).

3 Entrepreneurship

4

Southern Innovator Issue 1

Southern Innovator's first issue profiled pioneers and innovators using mobile phones and information technology to tackle poverty and meet the Millennium Development Goals. It was launched in May of 2011 and the print version was distributed around the world by the UNDP Special Unit for South-South Cooperation.

**Southern Innovator
#2 Available Now!**

MONEY, MONEY

- Where to Get It

MICRO-LENDERS

Kiva: A non-profit organization with a mission to connect people through lending to alleviate poverty. Leveraging the Internet and a worldwide network of microfinance institutions, Kiva lets individuals lend as little as US \$25 to help to create opportunity around the world. **Website:** kiva.org

United Prosperity: People can select the entrepreneur to support. Each US \$1 contributed acts as collateral or a loan guarantee with a bank. Based on the guarantee, the bank makes a loan of nearly US \$2 to the entrepreneur through a partner microfinance institution (MFI). Once a guarantee has been made, the entrepreneur's progress can be tracked online. On loan repayment, you receive your money and can choose to recycle it by guaranteeing the loan to another entrepreneur. **Website:** unitedprosperity.org

Grameen Foundation: Grameen Foundation helps the world's poorest, especially women, improve their lives and escape poverty by providing them with access to loans, essential information and viable business opportunities. Through two of the most effective tools known – small loans and the mobile phone – they work to make a real difference in the lives of those who have been left behind: poor people, especially those living on less than US \$1.25 per day. **Website:** grameenfoundation.org

GRANTS

Google.org: While SMEs in rich countries represent half of GDP, they are largely absent from the formal economies of developing countries. Today, there are trillions of investment dollars chasing returns – and SMEs are a potentially high-impact, high-return investment. However, only a trickle of this capital currently reaches SMEs in developing countries. **Google.org's** goal is to increase this flow. It wants to show that SMEs can be profitable investments and do this by focusing on lowering transaction costs, deepening capital markets to increase liquidity and catalysing capital for investment. **Website:** google.org

Echoing Green: Social Entrepreneurs Fund: To accelerate social change, Echoing Green invests in and supports outstanding emerging social entrepreneurs to launch new organizations that deliver bold, high-impact solutions. Through a two-year fellowship programme, it helps its network of visionaries develop new solutions to society's most difficult problems. To date, Echoing Green has invested nearly US \$30 million in seed funding to almost 500 social entrepreneurs and their innovative organizations. **Website:** echoinggreen.org

Bill and Melinda Gates Foundation: Guided by the belief that every life has equal value, the Bill & Melinda Gates Foundation works to help all people lead healthy, productive lives. In developing countries, it focuses on improving people's health and giving them the chance to lift themselves out of hunger and extreme poverty. The Foundation disburses grants to people in more than 100 countries. **Website:** gatesfoundation.org

Skoll Foundation: Skoll is one of the leading foundations in the field of social entrepreneurship. Over the past 10 years, it has awarded more than US \$250 million, including investments in 85 social entrepreneurs and 70 organizations on five continents around the world who are creating a

brighter future for underserved communities. In addition to grant-making, it funds a US \$20 million plus portfolio of programme-related and mission-aligned investments. **Website:** skollfoundation.org

Rockefeller Foundation: The Rockefeller Foundation supports work that expands opportunity and strengthens resilience to social, economic, health and environmental challenges to promote the well-being of humanity. **Website:** rockefellerfoundation.org

South-South Experience Exchange Facility: Supported by China, Denmark, India, Mexico, The Netherlands, Spain and the United Kingdom and now Colombia, the South-South Experience Exchange Facility is a multi-donor trust fund that promotes the idea that developing countries can learn from the successes of other developing countries in overcoming similar challenges. **Website:** southsouthcases.info

Landesa: Landesa helps millions of families receive assistance in gaining legal control over their land. Landesa works mainly in China and India and sub-Saharan Africa. Land rights are a great spur to wealth creation and give families a stake in growing local economies. **Website:** landesa.org

AWARDS

Said Global Entrepreneur Challenge: SGEC is a global business-plan challenge hosted by the University of Oxford's Said Business School. It is more than just a competition; based on the quality of an initial one-page business plan, applicants will receive mentorship and guidance from the University of Oxford's business students and alumni to help to grow the ideas into practical, 10-page business plans. These business plans will be entered into a final competition where winners will be selected from six global regions. **Website:** www.sbs.ox.ac.uk/centers/entrepreneurship/programmes/Pages/YouthBusinessDevelopment.aspx

InnoCentive: InnoCentive is a challenge to the world's inventors to find solutions to real scientific and technological problems affecting the poor and vulnerable. It is an open marketplace where anybody with a problem can post it, and rewards for effective solutions stretch up to US \$100,000. It uses rigorous intellectual property protection so that ideas are not used without credit being given to the inventor. **Website:** innocentive.com

Grand Challenges Canada: A grand challenge is a specific critical barrier that, if removed, would help to solve an important health problem in the developing world with a high likelihood of global impact through widespread implementation. Grand Challenges Canada awards funding to innovative solutions to five challenges. **Website:** grandchallenges.ca

The Pioneers of Prosperity Grant and Award: This competition is a partnership between the OTF Group and the John F. Templeton Foundation of the United States. It promotes companies in East Africa by identifying local role models that act as examples of sustainable businesses in their country/region. It is open to businesses from Burundi, Kenya, Rwanda, the United Republic of Tanzania and Uganda. Five pioneers will receive US \$50,000 to re-invest in their businesses. It is open to for-profit businesses that provide high wages to their workers and that operate in sustainable ways. **Website:** pioneersofprosperity.org/index.php

SOCIAL FUNDING AND PATIENT CAPITAL

Acumen Fund: Its mission is to create a world beyond poverty by investing in social enterprises, emerging leaders and breakthrough ideas. **Website:** acumenfund.org

Omidyar Network: A philanthropic investment firm. It creates opportunities to improve lives by investing in market-based efforts that catalyse economic, social and political change. **Website:** Omidyar.com

Ashoka: Innovators for the Public: Ashoka provides a wide range of services and funding for social entrepreneurs and now has over 2,000 Fellows in over 60 countries on five continents. **Website:** ashoka.org

Africa Entrepreneurship Platform: This groundbreaking initiative is created as a forum to showcase innovative ideas and businesses from Africa that have the ability to scale up internationally, driving job creation and sustainable economic development between Africa and the Americas. **Website:** sacca.biz

VENTURE CAPITAL

ClearlySo: ClearlySo connects social business, enterprise, commerce and investment. Its goal is to grow the social economy and help social entrepreneurs to raise capital and improve their core business skills. It helps investors to find exciting opportunities and introduce corporations to the social sector. **Website:** clearlyso.com

The Social Venture Forum: The Social Venture Forum was started with the objective of informing, inspiring and encouraging actions in favour of harmonious development through Social Venture in China. In addition to the portal, the Social Venture Forum aims to be a monthly event in Beijing. It gives people from a broad range of horizons, such as entrepreneurs, NGOs, researchers, investors, institutions representatives and the press an opportunity for networking in an ethical environment to meet, exchange ideas and build projects together. **Website:** socialventureforum.com

INVESTMENT FUNDS

African Agricultural Land Fund: The fund has raised almost €2 billion from an American pension fund to invest in African agriculture. The Africa Land Fund, created by the United Kingdom-based hedge fund Emergent Asset Management, wants to raise a total of €3 billion and is canvassing a range of investors. It plans to invest in agricultural land and livestock, including African game, which will be sold on to private reserves and safari parks. The Fund also plans to develop biofuel crops on marginal land, saving prime agricultural acreage for crops to feed people. **Website:** emergentasset.com/?func=Page

Aureos Africa Fund: Small and medium-sized enterprises across Africa are set to benefit from a multimillion dollar investment fund set up by private equity firm Aureos Capital with the Commonwealth Secretariat's assistance. The Aureos Africa Fund will provide long-term capital and support for promising and successful businesses across the continent. **Website:** aureos.com

BUSINESS SUPPORT

West Africa Trade Hub: The Hub works with people to improve transport, access to finance, the business environment and ICT to make West African businesses more competitive. **Website:** watradehub.com

ExportHelp - Promoting and supporting access to the European market: The European Commission runs a database for the explicit support of market players in developing countries who want to bring their products to the European Union market. The database gives an overview on the EU's preferential trade regimes established for developing countries and lists all tariffs, taxes and other requirements

for goods imported into the EU.

Website: exporthelp.europa.eu

African Diaspora Skills Database: This database was compiled to provide an overview of qualified African diaspora professionals with varied areas of expertise and experience. The African diaspora contributes substantially to the social, economic and political development of Africa, and this database is set up to further mobilize this considerable potential.

Website: diaspora-center.org

Development Executive Group Devex Networking:

Over 90,000 global experts can network and connect and learn about more than 47,000 registered projects. **Website:** devex.org

African Economic Outlook: A unique online tool that puts rigorous economic data, information and research on Africa at your fingertips. A few clicks give access to comprehensive analyses of African economies, placed in their social and political contexts. This is the only place where African countries are examined through a common analytical framework, allowing users to compare economic prospects at the regional, subregional and country levels.

Website: africaneconomicoutlook.org/en

TOOLKITS AND BUSINESS ADVICE

SME Toolkit Kenya.

Website: kenya.smetoolkit.org/kenya/en

HSBC Knowledge Center: News and know-how for your business. **Website:** knowledge.hsbc.co.uk

HSBC Business TV website.

Website: businessstv.hsbc.co.uk

SME Toolkit: Build Your Business.

Website: smetoolkit.org/smetoolkit/en

Branding Strategy Insider: Small businesses looking to develop their brand can find plenty of free advice and resources here.

Website: brandingstrategyinsider.com

Brandchannel: The world's only online exchange about branding, packed with resources, debates and contacts to help businesses to intelligently build their brand. **Website:** brandchannel.com

Just Food: A web portal full of the latest news on the global food industry and packed with events and special briefings to fill entrepreneurs in on the difficult issues and constantly shifting market demands. **Website:** just-food.com

Dutch Design in Development: DDiD will help Southern entrepreneurs and small enterprises to develop their brand and design identity and production processes by using experienced Dutch designers. **Website:** ddid.nl/english/index.html

Making Cents International: Making Cents' curricula are effective tools for creating, strengthening and supporting current and future entrepreneurs and delivering financial literacy for all. In over 25 languages, Making Cents offers a range of classroom materials to training institutions, schools and after-school programmes that strengthen the quality and impact of their business and entrepreneurship training and advisory services. **Website:** makingcents.com/products_services/curriculum.php

The resources listed here are for information purposes only and do not indicate an endorsement. When seeking funding, do the research and ask questions. If something sounds too good to be true, it probably is.

Quotables and Notables

- 01 “The youth bulge is happening and it is an enormous opportunity or an enormous challenge: how are all these young people going to have productive and valuable livelihoods and contribute to their communities?”, said **Fiona Macauley**, founder and president of Making Cents International, a US-based consulting firm working with entrepreneurs. “Policymakers are only just realizing they need a change of perspective on health issues, issues of poverty, the education system – all of it needs to respond.”
- 02 “We chose tech training because it’s a traditionally underrepresented area when it comes to reaching this particular group (underprivileged girls), yet such an important set of skills to be taught in this day and age... We want to expand these girls’ thinking – to get them interested in the possibilities of careers in science and tech rather than perpetuate the idea that all they’ll ever do, based on their circumstances, is tailoring or dance.” **Rachel Gichengo**, Kuweni Serious, Nairobi, Kenya.
- 03 “We are sitting in Addis Ababa but acting like an American company”, **Bethlehem Tilahun Alemu**, co-founder and managing director, soleRebels, Addis Ababa, Ethiopia, told *The Guardian* newspaper.
- 04 “Our concept was to harness a Pan African view of contemporary urban Africa. The pop art nature of African design inspired us to create our own-brand of coffee instead of the usual Italian coffee that most cafes use. Our goal was to refocus people to the origins of coffee – that it in fact originated in Africa before being discovered by the Arabs and from Yemen, exported around the world. Many people don’t know this, so we attempt to capture and celebrate this African spirit in our packaging and all we do”, **Grant Rushmere**, founder, Afrocoffee, Cape Town, South Africa, told *Ping Mag*.
- 05 Coffee can “create awareness that there’s recovery, there’s trade, there’s investment opportunities, there’s tourism. There’s life after death”, **Arthur Karuletwa**, co-founder, Bourbon Coffee, Kigali, Rwanda, told *The Washington Post*.
- 06 “In the old American business model, the relationships between a firm and its investors, bank, suppliers and customers tended to be very arm’s length...You would make a deal and report back after some specified period of time. The new business model is much more engaged. Everyone learns from one another, and there is a continuous flow of information. The firms are more specialized, but they see each other as collaborators”, said **Annalee Saxenian**, dean of the University of California, Berkeley’s School of Information.
- 07 “For decades, Africans have produced what they do not consume and consumed what they do not produce”, **Andrew Rugasira**, founder, Good African Coffee, Kampala, Uganda, told the *Wall Street Journal*.

Books, etc.

The Endless City and **Living in the Endless City** edited by Ricky Burdett and Deyan Sudjic, Publisher: Phaidon. Both books are excellent primers on the challenges facing the world's rapidly expanding cities.

Consumptiononomics: Asia's Role in Reshaping Capitalism and Saving the Planet by Chandran Nair, Publisher: Infinite Ideas. The book challenges Western development models for Asia.

World 3.0: Global Prosperity and How to Achieve It by Pankaj Ghemawa, Publisher: Harvard Business School Press. The book argues that the world is very different today than before the 2008 financial crisis.

Africa in the Global Economy by Richard E. Mshomba, Publisher: Lynne Rienner. An analysis of the role of international trade in Africa.

Creative Ecologies: Where Thinking Is a Proper Job by John Howkins, Publisher: UQP. Why do some ideas flourish and others fail? Why is independent thought valued in some societies and discouraged in others?

Arrival City by Doug Saunders, Publisher: Pantheon. A third of humanity is on the move. History's largest migration is the focus of this book.

State of the Field in Youth Enterprise, Employment and Livelihoods Development Publisher: Making Cents International. Best ways to engage youth for employment and enterprise.

Tourism and Poverty Reduction: Pathways to Prosperity by Jonathan Mitchell and Caroline Ashley, Publisher: Earthscan. This book provides an overview of a broad array of analyses of how tourism affects poor people.

Papers + Reports

Information Economy Report 2010: ICTs, Enterprises and Poverty Alleviation. Publisher: UNCTAD.

Website: unctad.org/Templates/webflyer.asp?docid=13912&intltemID=2068&lang=1

Trade and Development Report, 2010: Employment, Globalization and Development. Publisher: UNCTAD.

Website: unctad.org/Templates/webflyer.asp?docid=13740&intltemID=2068&lang=1

The Emerging Middle Class in Developing

Countries. Publisher: OECD.

Website: oecdilibrary.org/oecd/content/workingpaper/5kmmmp8lncrns-en

The BRICSAM Countries and Changing World Economic Power: Scenarios to 2050 by Manmohan Agarwal, Publisher: The Center for International Governance Innovation. Working Paper: Shifting Global Power. Africa and Mexico have the potential to change the balance of economic power in the world. This paper analyses this potential, building on developments in these economies over the past four decades in the context of the evolution of

the world economy. **Website:** cigionline.com/sites/default/files/Paper_39-web-1.pdf

Where Western business sees 'risk', Chinese entrepreneurs see opportunity by Dr. Jing Gu, Publisher: China-Africa Business Council (CABC) and the Chinese Academy of Social Sciences (CASS). Using its direct access to private Chinese companies working in Africa, the report includes 100 in-depth interviews with Chinese firms and business associations and officials in both China and Africa. **Website:** ids.ac.uk/go/news/where-western-business-sees-risk-chinese-entrepreneurs-see-opportunity

SI Online Content
www.southerninnovator.org

A wide range of online resources are available to Southern entrepreneurs through our various web-sites. Catch up on the past archive of stories through the **Southern Innovator** website. Read online, download or order a copy of **Southern Innovator** magazine. Also connect with the powerful resources available from the UNDP Special Unit for South-South Cooperation. These include knowledge-sharing resources through an academy, a yearly Expo for meeting and hearing from innovative Southern pioneers, and an online platform to obtain technology, assets and finance. Check it all out!

Southern Innovator website

The **Southern Innovator** website archive is home to stories going back to 2006. This site is intended to be a resource for sharing the solutions and innovations found in the South. It is also a tool for weaving and fostering South-South networking around the world.

Website: www.southerninnovator.org

South-South Global Assets and Technology Exchange

The SS-GATE is a virtual and physical platform where entrepreneurs in developing countries can interact and obtain needed technology, assets and finance in a secure environment. SS-GATE facilitates the realization of actual business transactions through a market mechanism, offering both online and offline beginning-to-end support services.

Website: www.ss-gate.org

Issue 1

Southern Innovator's first issue tackled the theme of mobile phones and information technology. It chronicled the rapid rise of mobile phones in Africa and featured pioneers using information technologies to achieve development goals and reduce poverty.

Issue 2

Southern Innovator's second issue provides a snapshot of innovators addressing the problem of youth unemployment and the role that entrepreneurship can play in engaging youth and boosting incomes and opportunities. It also profiles various business models using entrepreneurship to increase incomes and tackle poverty.

Global South-South Development Expo

The Global South-South Development Expo (GSSD Expo) is the first-ever Expo solely from the South and for the South. It showcases successful Southern-grown development solutions (SDSs) to address the need to meet the Millennium Development Goals (MDGs).

Website: www.southsouthexpo.org

Global South-South Development Academy

The Global South-South Development Academy is an online, action-oriented service platform that facilitates access to Southern development solutions and Southern expertise for learning and application.

Website: tcdc2.undp.org/GSSDAcademy

Youth

TREND

Youth Surge in the South: A Great Business Opportunity

Making Cents International: Making Cents International is a social enterprise based in Washington, D.C., that provides specialized technical services and curricula that enable entrepreneurs and enterprises to participate in profitable markets. **Website:** makingcents.com

Young Americas Business Trust – Latin America:

Acts as a “catalyst for young entrepreneur development in the Americas through business skills training, partnerships, leadership and technology”. **Website:** mybiz.net/yabt/main

Youth Business International (UK): An international organization providing disadvantaged youth with business mentoring and funds. **Website:** youthbusiness.org

UN Youth Employment Network: YEN works to engage, educate and motivate people to provide improved employment opportunities for youth. **Website:** ilo.org/public/english/employment/yen

African Youth Want to Do Business in Fast-growing Economy

Gallup surveys. **Website:** gallup.com

The Economic Report on Africa 2011. **Website:** uneca.org/era2011

Dutch Design in Development: DdID is the agency for fair design, sustainable production and fair trade. It works with Dutch importers and designers and connects them to local producers in developing countries and emerging markets. Together, products are made that are both profitable and socially and environmentally sustainable. **Website:** ddid.nl

MUSIC

Berber Hip Hop Helps to Re-ignite Culture and Economy

Boulevard des Jeunes Musiciens. **Website:** boulevard.ma

International Young Music Entrepreneur of the Year Award: an award from the British Council. **Website:** creativeeconomy.org.uk/UKYCE/index.asp?ID=35

The United Nations of Hip Hop: A web portal for African hip-hop news, music and resources. **Website:** unitednationsofhiphop.com

Festival Timitar: The Timitar music festival happens every year in July in Morocco's Agadir. **Website:** festival-timitar.com/timitar.html

Amazigh Film Festival: The annual Amazigh Film Festival takes place every year in January in Los Angeles, California, USA. **Website:** tukshop.biz

Taxis Promote African Music Beats

International Federation of the Phonographic Industry. **Website:** ifpi.org

University of Pretoria. **Website:** web.up.ac.za

YouTube: The online channel allows anyone to upload music videos to share with the world. **Website:** youtube.com

DJ Mujava: Listen to all of DJ Mujava's tracks on his website. **Website:** myspace.com/mujava

DigiArts Africa: The DigiArts Africa network is a tool to find people working

in digital arts in Africa.

Website: portal.unesco.org/culture/en/ev.php-URL_ID=5346&URL_DO=DO_TOPIC&URL_SECTION=201.html

African Musicians Profiles: A lively website featuring profiles of African musicians by alphabetical listing and reviews of African films. **Website:** africanmusiciansprofiles.com

Recording Industry of South Africa (RISA): RISA is the main body representing the South African recording industry. **Website:** risa.org.za

Ring Tones and Mobile Phone Downloads Are Generating Income for Local Musicians in Africa

Orange Botswana. **Website:** orange.co.bw

CREATIVE ECONOMY

Bolivian Film School's Film Scene Paying Off

Cine Alto film school at the Municipal Arts School of El Alto. **Website:** cinealto.blogspot.com/2009/01/nueva-carrera-de-arte-cinematograficas.html

Spanish film “Even the Rain”. **Website:** tambienlalluvia.com

Cannes Film Festival. **Website:** festival-cannes.com

European film festival in Bolivia. **Website:** cineuropeobolivia.org

Cine Alto on Facebook. **Website:** es-la.facebook.com/cine.alto

AltoTV: A non-profit television documentary-making project that has made small films on El Alto. **Website:** altotvgerman.blogspot.com

The Public University of El Alto. **Website:** enlaupea.com

Creative Economy Report 2008: An economic and statistical assessment of creative industries world-wide as well as an overview of how developing countries can benefit from trade in creative products and services. **Website:** unctad.org/en/docs/ditc20082cer_en.pdf

A course on Bolivian filmmaking taught by award-winning filmmaker, Ismael Saavedra. **Website:** sit.edu/studyabroad/sss_blv.cfm

Filmmaking Resources

- **Tips on Filmmaking**
- **BBC Filmmaking Guide.** **Website:** bbc.co.uk/filmnetwork/filmmaking

Making the Film: Quick Start Guide To Filmmaking. **Website:** makingthefilm.com/guide.html

Guide Book for Guerrilla Filmmakers. **Website:** jamesarnett.com/sections.html

Digital Filmmaking Blog. **Website:** digital-filmmaking.blogspot.com

• **Movie-sharing Resources:**

Vimeo. **Website:** vimeo.com

You Tube. **Website:** youtube.com

Live Leak. **Website:** liveleak.com

Qik. **Website:** qik.com

Vimessa. **Website:** vimessa.com

Socialcam. **Website:** socialcam.com

Local Animation: A Way Out of Poverty

Africa Animated: Initiative for African Cartoon Production: This UNESCO initiative brings together African artists and the audiovisual industry to increase production in Africa. **Website:** africancolours.com

AnimationSA.org: The South African

Animation Directory: The official website for the South African animation industry, it hosts a great deal of information on jobs, training, events and developments. **Website:** animationsa.org

Animation World Network: This is the global networking portal for the world's animation industry and is packed with news, jobs, tips and training opportunities. **Website:** awn.com

Old Adage Gets New Life

TeachAManToFish. **Website:** teachamantofish.org.uk

Fundacion Paraguaya – San Francisco Agricultural High School. **Website:** fundacionparaguaya.org.py

Cambodian Bloggers Champion New, Open Ways

Cloggers scene: A presentation about the Cloggers scene and how it works. **Website:** slideshare.net/kalyaneko/cloggers-life-an-introduction-to-cambodian-blogosphere

Khmer Rouge. **Website:** en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Khmer_Rouge

Blue Lady Blog. **Website:** blueladyblog.com

TEDx. **Website:** tedxphnompenh.com

Clogger Summit. **Website:** cloggersummit.wikispaces.com

Reporters Without Borders. **Website:** en.rsf.org

Afrinnovator: Is about telling the stories of African start-ups, African innovation, African-made technology, African tech entrepreneurship and entrepreneurs. **Website:** afrinnovator.com

Changing Dynamics of Global Computer Software and Services Industry: Implications for Developing Countries: A report from UNCTAD on how computer software can become the most internationally dispersed high-tech industry. **Website:** unctad.org/templates/webflyer.asp?docid=1913&intitemid=2529&lang=1

Business Link: Advice on starting a business and succeeding in tough economic times. **Website:** businesslink.gov.uk/bdotg/actionlayer?topicId=1073858805

Ger Magazine: Mongolia's first online magazine in the late 1990s contributed to the country's vibrant web culture. **Website:** en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Ger_magazine

Phnom Penh Post: English-language newspaper. **Website:** phnompenhpost.com

Turning African Youth on to Technology

Southern Innovator magazine: New global magazine **Southern Innovator's** first issue is about mobile phones and information technology in the global South. **Website:** scribd.com/doc/57980406/Southern-Innovator-Issue-1

Cashing in on Music in Brazil

International Federation of the Phonographic Industry. **Website:** www.ifpi.org

iTunes. **Website:** apple.com/downloads

Mash-up. **Website:** en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Mashups

Creative Commons Brazil. **Website:** creativecommons.org/international/br

About Belem, Brazil. **Website:** en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Bel%C3%A9m

Bringing the Invention and Innovation Mindset to Young Kenyans

PicoCrickets: A PicoCricket is a tiny computer that can make things spin, light up and play music. **Website:** picocricket.com

Lifelong Kindergarten group: It develops new technologies that, in the spirit of the blocks and fingerpaint of kindergarten, expand the range of what people can design, create and learn. **Website:** llk.media.mit.edu

MIT Media Lab: The MIT Media Lab applies an unorthodox research approach to envision the impact of emerging technologies on everyday life—technologies that promise to fundamentally transform our most basic notions of human capabilities. **Website:** media.mit.edu

Girl Effect: Girl Effect is a movement driven by girl champions around the globe. **Website:** girleffect.org

Ushahidi: A non-profit tech company that specializes in developing free and open source software for information collection, visualization and interactive mapping. **Website:** ushahidi.com

Kuweni Serious: A movement to show that Kenyan youth are not apathetic. **Website:** kuweniserious.org

ZanaAfrica: ZanaAfrica equips Kenyan girls and women to become the next generation of leaders in their communities by creating simple solutions to address root causes of gender inequality. **Website:** zanaa.org

Turning Street Children into Entrepreneurs

The Children's Development Bank. **Website:** childrensdevelopmentbank.org

Youth Bank. **Website:** youthbank.org.uk

Urban Youth: A Great Source of Untapped Growth

KickStart is a South African project aimed at inculcating a culture of entrepreneurship among young people between the ages of 18 and 35. **Website:** sabbickstart.co.za

iDISC – the infoDev Incubator Support Center – is a virtual networking and knowledge-sharing platform for incubators and technology parks leveraging ICT to facilitate entrepreneurship and new business creation in developing countries. **Website:** idisc.net/en/Index.html

Entrepreneurship

INNOVATION

Innovation from the Global South

The **Atlas of Ideas** is an 18-month study of science and innovation in China, India and the Republic of Korea, with a special focus on new opportunities for collaboration with Europe. **Website:** demos.co.uk/projects/atlasofideas

Entrepreneurship Development Institute of India: The Entrepreneurship Development Institute of India (EDI), an autonomous body and not-for-profit

Contacts and Resources

institution, was set up in 1983.

Website: ediindia.org
Innovation Works (China): Innovation Works (IW) is China's premier incubator for tech start-ups, based in Beijing and in Shanghai. **Website:** crunchbase.com/financial-organization/innovation-works-china

Dynamic Growth in African ICT Is Unlocking Secrets of SME Treasure Trove

Towards an African e-Index: SME e-Access and Usage in 14 African Countries.
Website: scribd.com/doc/59824810/Towards-An-African-E-Index
Research ICT Africa: The Research ICT Africa Network conducts research on ICT policy and regulation that facilitates evidence-based and informed policymaking for improved access, use and application of ICT for social development and economic growth. **Website:** researchictafrica.net

Social Franchising Models Proving Poor Bring Profits

C.K. Prahalad: A summary of the work and ideas of C.K. Prahalad. **Website:** en.wikipedia.org/wiki/C._K._Prahalad
World Resources Institute: The World Resources Institute is a global environmental think tank that goes beyond research to put ideas into action. **Website:** wri.org
The Next 4 Billion: The Next 4 Billion uses previously unreleased data to measure market opportunity at the bottom of the pyramid. **Website:** wri.org/publication/the-next-4-billion
World Health Organization's Vision 2020 campaign. Vision 2020 is the global initiative for the elimination of avoidable blindness. **Website:** vision2020.org
VisionSpring (formerly Scojo Foundation): VisionSpring is an innovative social enterprise dedicated to reducing poverty and generating opportunity in the developed world through the sale of affordable eyeglasses. **Website:** scojofoundation.org
Acumen Fund: Acumen Fund's vision is to create a world beyond poverty by investing in social enterprises, emerging leaders and breakthrough ideas. **Website:** acumenfund.org

Microwork Pioneer

Mechanical Turk: This is an income-generating tool run by online book sellers Amazon.com. It pays people for spending time online transcribing audio recordings and tagging photos. **Website:** mturk.com/mturk/welcome

FUNDING

Business as a Tool to Do Good
Grameen Bank: Grameen Bank (GB) has reversed conventional banking practice by removing the need for collateral and created a banking system based on mutual trust, accountability, participation and creativity. **Website:** grameen-info.org
The Skoll Center for Social Entrepreneurship at Oxford's Said Business School hosts the Skoll World Forum every year to promote entrepreneurial solutions to social problems. **Website:** sbs.ox.ac.uk/centers/skoll/Pages/default.aspx

Ashoka: Ashoka is the global association of the world's leading social entrepreneurs. **Website:** ashoka.org
Social Ventures Partners: While only focused on the Seattle, USA area, SVP offers a model that can be applied throughout the global South. The vision of the founders was to build a philanthropic organization using a venture capital model, where partners actively nurture their financial investments with guidance and resources. **Website:** svpseattle.org
Generation Investment Management: Started in 2004 with former US vice president Al Gore, they focus only on investments that are long-term, sustainable and that they really believe in. **Website:** generationim.com
Omidyar Network: Started by Ebay's founders, it funds for-profits and non-profits that promote equal access to information, tools and opportunities and encourage shared interests and a sense of ownership among participants. **Website:** omidyar.net
Skoll Foundation: The mission of the Foundation is to seek out social entrepreneurs who are already implementing successful programmes on a small scale. **Website:** skollfoundation.org
SV2: Silicon Valley Social Venture Fund: A partnership of successful technology entrepreneurs, it pools funds to support social entrepreneurs by giving money and giving time – venture philanthropy. **Website:** sv2.org
Google.org: It uses the talent, technology and financial resources of the successful search engine to tackle global poverty. **Website:** google.org
Acumen Fund: A non-profit venture fund that invests in market-based solutions to global poverty. **Website:** acumenfund.org
TechnoServe: Helps budding entrepreneurs turn good business ideas into thriving enterprises. **Website:** technoserve.org

Accessing Global Markets via Design Solutions

Dutch Design in Development: DDiD is the agency for fair design, sustainable production and fair trade. It works with Dutch importers and designers and connects them to local producers in developing countries and emerging markets. **Website:** ddid.nl/english
Design for the Other 90%: An exhibition exploring a growing movement among designers to design low-cost solutions for the "other 90%" ignored by most products and services. **Website:** archive.cooperhewitt.org/other90/other90.cooperhewitt.org
Ferry Meewisse also blogged in Dutch about his experience here. **Website:** ferryinindia.blogspot.com
Havaianas: The Brazilian flip-flop maker Havaianas has become a global phenomenon with its unique, design-savvy business model. **Website:** havaianas.com.br
Veja: Shoes produced in a partnership between a French shoe maker and Brazilian farmers and inspired by 1970s Brazilian volleyball stars' shoes. **Website:** veja.fr
Red Dot: The red dot logo stands for belonging to the best in design and business. The red dot is an internationally recognized quality label for excellent

design that is aimed at all those who would like to improve their business activities with the help of design. **Website:** red-dot.de

Women Mastering Trade Rules

Mobile Active: Book on how mobile phones are empowering women in Nigeria: *Mobile Telephony: Leveraging Strengths and Opportunities for Socio-Economic Transformation in Nigeria.* **Website:** mobileactive.org/book-review-nigeria-goes-mobile
Business Action for Africa: This is a network of businesses and business organizations working collectively to accelerate growth and poverty reduction in Africa. **Website:** businessactionforafrica.org

African Trade Hub in China Brings Mutual Profits

World Trade Organization (WTO): It is an organization for opening up trade. It is a forum for governments to negotiate trade agreements and to settle trade disputes. It operates a system of trade rules. **Website:** wto.org
Africa-China Trade: A *Financial Times* report on Africa-China trade in 2010. **Website:** ft.com/reports/africa-china-trade-2010
Africa Town: An article about "Africa Town" can be found on the official Guangzhou website. **Website:** lifeofguangzhou.com
Trade Winds: *Guangzhou's African Community* by Graeme Nicol is a photo book about the community. **Website:** graemenicol.com/?page_id=115

TRADE

Rainforest Rubbers Save Lives Health Ministry of Brazil.

Website: portal.saude.gov.br/saude
Acree State: More news on developments in the State of Acree. **Website:** agenciadenoticias.ac.gov.br

Africa's Consumer Market Growing Fast

Afrique Avenir: Inspiring blog tracking Africa's rising middle class and its global economic impact. **Website:** afriqueavenir.org/en
Afro Coffee: A design-savvy South African coffee shop chain that has expanded to Europe. It uses a modern African-themed design in its shops and product range. **Website:** afrocoffee.com
Africa Rising: A book by Professor Vijay Mahajan on how Africa's consumer economy is growing and growing. **Website:** tinyurl.com/2vk3m9n
Arise Magazine: Arise is a Nigerian style monthly started by Nigerian media mogul Nduka Obaigbena, who also publishes Nigeria's leading newspaper, *This Day*. **Website:** arisemagazine.net
African Consumer Market: A video on the rising African consumer market. **Website:** annansi.com/blog/2010/12/growth-and-spending-of-african-consumer-video
Annansi Chronicles: A blog packed with the latest news and media on trends in African business and culture. **Website:** annansi.com/blog
Africa's New Wealth: An interactive map of Africa's new wealth and where to find it. **Website:** online.wsj.com/article/SB10001424052748704720804576009672053184168.html#project%3DAFRICAMAP011%26articleTabs%3Dinteractive

Indonesia Best for Entrepreneurs Entrepreneurship Survey.

Website: globescan.com/news_archives/bbc2011_entrepreneur/background.html
Alibaba: An online marketplace for trading and buying and selling goods. **Website:** alibaba.com
Zopa: Zopa is an online marketplace that matches people with money to invest with borrowers who need a personal loan. **Website:** zopa.com
Kiva: A non-profit organization with a mission to connect people through lending to alleviate poverty. Leveraging the Internet and a worldwide network of microfinance institutions, Kiva lets individuals lend as little as \$25 to help create opportunity around the world. **Website:** kiva.org
Betterplace: People who want to help meet people who are in need of support on this online donation platform. **Website:** betterplace.org
Kickstarter: The world's largest funding platform for creative projects. **Website:** kickstarter.com

• Small Business Guide:

An online resource packed with advice and resources on starting a small business. **Website:** smallbusiness.co.uk

SME Toolkits Abound: Here are two from Africa: **SME Toolkit Kenya.** **Website:** kenya.smetoolkit.org/kenya/en and **SME Toolkit South Africa.** **Website:** southafrica.smetoolkit.org/sa/en
African Capital Alliance: African Capital Alliance (ACA) is a leading private equity firm focused on Nigeria and West Africa. **Website:** aca-web.com
World Business Fair: The World Business Fair is an international trade platform for global entrepreneurs and professionals. **Website:** worldbusinessfair.com
Branding Strategy: Small businesses looking to develop their brand can find plenty of free advice and resources here. **Website:** brandingstrategyinsider.com
Brandchannel: The world's only online exchange about branding, packed with resources, debates and contacts to help businesses intelligently build their brand. **Website:** brandchannel.com
ZanaAfrica (ZanaA) is a non-profit whose mission is to craft tools from within Africa to slay the giants of poverty. The tools are in the nexus of health, education and environment, with a particular focus on gender and technology. **Website:** zanaa.org
Small Business in Indonesia by Peter Van Diermen. Explores how critical families are to business success in Indonesia. **Website:** books.google.com/books/about/Small_business_in_Indonesia.html?id=WSu1AAAIAAJ
SME Toolkit Indonesia: The SME Toolkit Indonesia offers a wide range of how-to articles, business forms, free business software, online training, self-assessment exercises, quizzes and other resources to help entrepreneurs, business owners and managers in emerging markets and developing countries start, finance, formalize and grow their businesses. **Website:** indonesia.smetoolkit.org/indonesia/en

Mongolian Enterprises Target Healthy Urban Lifestyles

Mongolian Food: Meat, milk and Mongolia: An article from the UNDP online magazine, Ger, published in the late 1990s. **Website:** mongoluls.net/ger/meatmilk.shtml
Global Food Security Crisis: A joint UN website with frequent updates on the global food crisis and how to respond. **Website:** un-foodsecurity.org
Ananda Yoga Center: Part of the increasing awareness of the importance of a healthy lifestyle, this yoga and meditation center is located in Ulaanbaatar, Mongolia. **Website:** yogamongolia.org

Model City to Test the New Urbanism Concept in India

"Urbanized": New documentary "Urbanized" gives a passionate overview of the challenges facing the rapidly urbanizing world around us. **Website:** urbanizedfilm.com
Global Urbanist: Excellent expert-contributed website by alumni from the London School of Economics and Political Science (LSE). **Website:** globalurbanist.com

Shoes with Sole: Ethiopian Web Success Story

Café Press: The online service CafePress is a specially designed one-stop shop that lets entrepreneurs upload their designs and then sell them via their online payment and worldwide shipping service. **Website:** cafepress.com/cp/info/sell
Fashionmag.com: Once you are inspired to get into the global fashion business, check out this business website for all the latest news, jobs and events. **Website:** us.fashionmag.com/news/index.php
iFashion: This web portal run from South Africa has all the latest business news on fashion in Africa and profiles of up-and-coming designers. **Website:** ifashion.co.za/index.php?option=com_frontpage&Itemid=1
Havianas: A Brazilian global fashion success with its rubber flip flops. **Website:** havaianas.com
Arise Africa Fashion Week: The place to be seen and to see. **Website:** africanfashioninternational.com/africaFashionWeek
 Once inspired to get into the **global fashion business**, check out this business website for all the latest news, jobs and events. **Website:** us.fashionmag.com/news/index.php

Solar Sisters Doing It for Themselves: Tackling African Light Famine

Solar Sister. Website: solarsister.org
D.light Design: Their lights use LEDs (light-emitting diodes) (en.wikipedia.org/wiki/LED_lamp) and are four times brighter than a kerosene lantern according to D.Light Design. **Website:** dlightdesign.com
Lighting Africa: Lighting Africa, a joint IFC and World Bank programme, is helping to develop commercial off-grid lighting markets in sub-Saharan Africa as part of the World Bank Group's wider efforts to improve access to energy. **Website:** lightingafrica.org
Solar Lighting for the Base of the Pyramid – Overview of an Emerging

Market, a report by the International Finance Corporation finding that Africa will be the world's largest market for solar portable lights by 2015. The report addresses market trends and statistics at a global level with more detailed analysis for the African market. **Website:** lightingafrica.org/market-intelligence/market-trends-assessment.html

How We Made It in Africa: A website detailing success stories on businesses investing in Africa and how people are making the most of opportunities on the continent. **Website:** howwemadeitinafrica.com

Barefoot College: The College is training women to be solar engineers, developing both useful skills and a new income source. **Website:** barefootcollege.org

Solar Power Answers is a one-stop-shop for everything to do with solar power. It has a design manual and guides to the complex world of solar power equipment. **Website:** solar-power-answers.co.uk/index.php

Sun King Solar Lantern: The lantern provides 16 hours of light from a day's charge. **Website:** greenlightplanet.com/ourusers.html

ToughStuff has developed a modular range of affordable solar-powered energy solutions to the three main power needs of poor consumers in the developing world: lighting, mobile phones and radios. **Website:** toughstuffonline.com

South African Wine Industry Uncorks Opportunities

Thandi Wines: Established in Elgin, South Africa in 1995, Thandi's aim is to empower previously disadvantaged farming communities. **Website:** thandi.com
M'hudi: The name M'hudi is derived from the Setswana word, "mohudi", meaning "harvester". The Rangaka family founded the M'hudi brand and are the main characters of the M'hudi Wines adventure. **Website:** mhudi.com
Seven Sisters: The Seven Sisters wine brand evolved from its association with the seven Brutus sisters of Paternoster. **Website:** sevensisters.co.za/wmnuu.php
Indaba Wines: The brand was created as a celebration of the democratization process in South Africa, and from its inception, the wines have conveyed the spirit of South Africa to American consumers. **Website:** indabawines.com

Putting Quality and Design at the Centre of Chinese Fashion

Ecodesignfair: Eco Design Fair is a bi-annual grass-roots community event whose purpose is to showcase eco-conscious designers and products to general consumers. **Website:** ecodesignfair.cn
Nest: Another eco-conscious design company in Shanghai. Its motto is "design with a conscience". **Website:** nestshanghai.com/nest.html

Mapping Beirut Brings City to Light

Zawarib Beirut Road Atlas: The Zawarib Beirut can be purchased from Amazon's website.

Website: amazon.co.uk/Zawarib-Beirut-Greater-Atlas/dp/9953005311

Google Maps: A treasure trove of global maps and data. **Website:** maps.google.co.uk
Google Street View: A global database of photographs showing neighbourhoods and streets. **Website:** maps.google.com/intl/en/help/maps/streetview/#utm_campaign=en&utm_medium=van&utm_source=en-van-na-us-gns-svn
Google Maps for Mobile: Use Google Maps on your phone and never carry a paper map again. **Website:** google.co.uk/mobile/maps

Ghana's Funeral Economy Innovates and Exports

ShopAfrica53: Pledging in its motto to reach "every African nook and cranny", ShopAfrica53 is an online shopping portal similar to famous brands such as Amazon or eBay, but focused entirely on giving African traders the ability to sell across the continent and to the world online. **Website:** shopafrica53.com
Going into Darkness: Fantastic Coffins from Africa by Thierry Secretan details the culture and the craftsmen behind the iconic coffins. **Website:** amazon.com/exec/obidos/ASIN/0500278393/cordelinetwebstu

Creative Economy Programme: The creative economy is an emerging concept dealing with the interface between creativity, culture, economics and technology in a contemporary world dominated by images, sounds, texts and symbols. **Website:** unctad.org/Templates/StartPage.asp?intitemID=4577&lang=1

Afro Coffee: Blending Good Design and Coffee

Afro Coffee: The Afro Coffee website has more on the company and sells its many products. **Website:** afrocoffee.com
Design Indaba: Since 1995, Design Indaba has been committed to a vision that is built on the belief that creativity will fuel an economic revolution in South Africa. **Website:** designindaba.com
Brandchannel: The world's only online exchange about branding, packed with resources, debates and contacts to help businesses to intelligently build their brand. **Website:** brandchannel.com

Branding Strategy Insider: Small businesses looking to develop their brand can find resources at Branding Strategy Insider. **Website:** brandingstrategyinsider.com
Dutch Design in Development: Dutch designers are able to offer free support to new and small businesses in developing countries looking to export products to Europe. **Website:** ddid.nl

Rwandan Coffee Brand Boost

Bourbon Coffee: Bourbon Coffee is an international brand of specialty coffee and the first retail brand to originate from Africa. **Website:** bourboncoffeeusa.com
Bourbon Coffee Varietal: More on the specific bourbon coffee varietal. **Website:** en.wikipedia.org/wiki/List_of_coffee_varieties
Tristar Investments: Tri-Star Investments (Tri-Star) is an indigenous Rwandan company established in 1994

by a group of Rwandans who pooled resources in an effort to overcome the tremendous challenges of rebuilding the domestic economy in the aftermath of the genocide.

Website: tri-starinvestments.com/index.html
Rwandan Farmers Brand: Rwandan Farmers is a unique brand, owned in trust for Rwandan farmers where all of its profits are returned to the very people who toil daily in the fields of Rwanda. **Website:** rwandanfarmers.com
East African Fine Coffees Association: All the latest news on events and initiatives for East Africa's coffee producers. **Website:** eafca.org
Red Dot: The red dot logo stands for belonging to the best in design and business. The red dot is an internationally recognized quality label for excellent design that is aimed at all those who would like to improve their business activities with the help of design. **Website:** red-dot.de

Good African Coffee Brews Instant Success

Good African Coffee: The online presence of the company, displaying its coffees for sale. **Website:** goodafrican.com/index.php/our-story/trade-not-aid.html

Additional Resources

- **Youth Entrepreneurship-Closing the Gap:** "Closing the Gap" comprises nine case studies each of which illustrates how the finance "gap" can be closed for underserved entrepreneurs through providing non-financial support, such as training and mentoring. **Website:** youthecommopportunities.org/media.asp
- **Entrepreneurship Entrepreneur:** A website packed with resources to help small businesses from start-up to growth and how to obtain funding. **Website:** entrepreneur.com

Key Terms and Abbreviations

Apps: An abbreviation for "application". An app is a piece of software. It can run on the Internet, on your computer or on your phone or other electronic device.
Caveat emptor: Noun: The principle that the buyer is responsible for checking the quality and suitability of goods before a purchase is made (*Oxford Dictionary*).
Duty of care: The legal obligation for an individual to adhere to a standard of reasonable care while performing any acts that could foreseeably harm others.
Entrepreneur: Noun: A person who sets up a business or businesses, taking on financial risks in the hope of profit; a promoter in the entertainment industry (*Oxford Dictionary*).
Logo: Noun: A symbol or other small design by an organization to identify its products, uniform, vehicles, etc. (*Oxford Dictionary*).
UNDP: The United Nations Development Programme is the United Nations' global development network.

NEXT ISSUE OF Southern Innovator

AGRICULTURE AND FOOD SECURITY

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